

1 **Thematic issue** ST 46 - Voices & Beyond: Interdisciplinary Advances & Applications in Prosody
2 Research

3
4 **Category of Contribution:** Pilot Study

5
6 **The influence of prosodic-acoustic features in automatic speech recognition of two inland**
7 **Brazilian dialects: A pilot study**

8
9 **A influência de parâmetros prosódico-acústicos no reconhecimento automático de fala em**
10 **dois dialetos do interior brasileiro: Um estudo piloto**

11
12 *Leônidas Silva Jr.*

13 State University of Paraíba – UEPB, Department of Modern Languages, Guarabira-PB.
14 Federal University of Pernambuco – UFPE, Graduate Program in Language and Literature, Recife-PE.

15 *Corresponding author's e-mail: leonidas.silvajr@gmail.com

16 ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3728-9851> | [CV lattes](#)

17
18 *Luciani E. Tenani*

19 State University of São Paulo – UNESP, Department of Language and Literature Studies, São José do Rio Preto-SP

20 E-mail: luciani.tenani@unesp.br

21 ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8487-0825> | [CV lattes](#)

22
23 *João Marcelo Monte*

24 Pernambuco Water and Sewage Company – COMPESA, Department of Operational Technology, Recife-PE

25 E-mail: joaommsilva@gmail.com

26 ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3124-4062> | [CV lattes](#)

27
28 **Author Contributions (CRediT taxonomy)**

- 29 **1. Leônidas Silva Jr.:** Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Formal analysis; Data
30 curation; Visualization; Project administration; Writing – Original Draft; Writing – Review
31 & Editing.
- 32 **2. Luciani E. Tenani:** Investigation; Resources; Validation; Data curation; Writing – Original
33 Draft; Writing – Review & Editing; Funding acquisition.
- 34 **3. João Marcelo Monte:** Software; Validation; Supervision; Writing – Original Draft;
35 Writing – Review & Editing.

36
37 **Abstract**

38 This study investigates the role of prosodic-acoustic features in distinguishing two inland varieties of
39 Brazilian Portuguese, Paraíba (PB) and São Paulo (SP), and examines how these features influence
40 automatic speech recognition (ASR) performance. Grounded in sociophonetic theory and dialect-aware
41 speech modeling (Mehralian; Van Hamme, 2025; Torgbi et al., 2025; Thomas, 2011; Wassink; Gansen;
42 Bartholomew, 2022), this pilot study evaluates whether prosodic-acoustic descriptors of duration,
43 fundamental frequency (f0), and intensity provide robust cues for dialect differentiation and to what extent
44 automatic dialect classification can be explained by the relative contribution of these acoustic dimensions
45 (Esling; Edmondson, 2011; Yaeger-Dror; Fagyal, 2011). The study integrates two complementary
46 methodological stages. Methodology 1 encompasses corpus design, acoustic extraction procedures, and
47 inferential statistical modeling. Twenty university students (ten per dialect) produced controlled reading
48 recordings, yielding 460 speech samples. Prosodic-acoustic parameters were extracted and analyzed using
49 Linear Mixed-Effects Models to identify statistically significant dialect differences while controlling for
50 inter-speaker variability. Methodology 2 applies automatic dialect classification using six machine-learning

51 classifiers to evaluate the discriminative capacity of those features. The results are presented in two stages.
52 Results 1 demonstrate that duration-related measures—particularly pause variability—provide the strongest
53 explanatory power for distinguishing PB and SP, followed by intensity-related parameters such as spectral
54 tilt and intensity variation coefficient, whereas f_0 measures show comparatively smaller effects. Results 2
55 show that classification accuracy ranges from 94.6% to 97.8%, with tree-based models achieving the highest
56 performance. Feature-importance analyses reveal a hierarchical contribution of acoustic parameters
57 dominated by rhythmic-temporal organization. The convergence between explanatory statistical modeling
58 and predictive classification demonstrates that inland dialect differentiation in Brazilian Portuguese is
59 acoustically structured, prosodically organized, and computationally detectable. These findings contribute
60 to the sociophonetic description of inland Brazilian Portuguese varieties and provide empirical grounding
61 for incorporating dialect-sensitive prosodic modeling into ASR systems.

62
63 **Keywords:** Prosodic-acoustic features; Dialect classification; Automatic speech recognition; Brazilian
64 Portuguese; Sociophonetics.

65 66 **Resumo**

67 Este estudo investiga o papel de parâmetros prosódico-acústicos na distinção de duas variedades dialetais
68 do interior brasileiro, na Paraíba (PB) e em São Paulo (SP), e examina como tais parâmetros influenciam o
69 desempenho de sistemas de reconhecimento automático de fala. Fundamentado em estudos da Sociofonética
70 e na modelagem de fala automática sensível à variação dialetal (Mehralian; Van Hamme, 2025; Torgbi et
71 al., 2025; Thomas, 2011; Wassink; Gansen; Bartholomew, 2022), este estudo piloto avalia se descritores
72 prosódico-acústicos de duração, frequência fundamental (f_0) e intensidade constituem pistas robustas para
73 a diferenciação dialetal e em que medida a classificação automática de dialetos pode ser explicada pela
74 contribuição relativa dessas dimensões acústicas (Esling; Edmondson, 2011; Yaeger-Dror; Fagyal, 2011).
75 A pesquisa integra duas etapas metodológicas complementares. A Metodologia 1 envolve o desenho do
76 corpus, os procedimentos de extração acústica e a modelagem estatística inferencial. Vinte estudantes
77 universitários (dez por dialeto) produziram gravações de leitura controlada, totalizando 460 amostras de
78 fala. Os parâmetros prosódico-acústicos foram extraídos e analisados por meio de Modelos Lineares de
79 Efeitos Mistos, a fim de identificar diferenças dialetais estatisticamente significativas, controlando a
80 variabilidade interindividual. A Metodologia 2 aplica a classificação automática de dialetos por meio de seis
81 classificadores baseados em aprendizado de máquina, com o objetivo de avaliar a capacidade discriminativa
82 dessas características acústicas. Os resultados são apresentados em duas etapas. Resultados 1 indicam que
83 medidas relacionadas à duração, especialmente a variabilidade de pausas, apresentaram maior poder
84 explicativo na distinção entre PB e SP, seguidas por parâmetros de intensidade, como o declive espectral e
85 o coeficiente de variação da intensidade, enquanto medidas baseadas em f_0 exibiram efeitos
86 comparativamente menores. Resultados 2 mostram que a acurácia da classificação automática variou entre
87 94,6% e 97,8%, com modelos baseados em árvores apresentando o melhor desempenho. A hierarquização
88 da importância das variáveis confirmou a predominância de parâmetros rítmico-temporais no processo de
89 classificação. A convergência entre modelagem estatística explicativa e classificação preditiva demonstra
90 que a diferenciação dialetal entre variedades do interior do Brasil é acusticamente estruturada,
91 hierarquicamente organizada e computacionalmente detectável. Esses resultados contribuem para a
92 descrição sociofonética das variedades dialetais do interior do português brasileiro e oferecem
93 fundamentação empírica para a incorporação de modelagem prosódica sensível à variação dialetal em
94 sistemas de reconhecimento automático de fala.

95
96 **Palavras-chave:** Parâmetros prosódico-acústicos; Classificação dialetal; Reconhecimento automático de
97 fala; Português brasileiro; Sociofonética.

98 99 **Lay Summary**

100 This study explores how speech rhythm, pitch, and voice quality help distinguish two regional varieties of
101 Brazilian Portuguese spoken in inland Paraíba and inland São Paulo. While people can usually recognize

102 regional accents easily, automatic speech recognition systems often struggle when speech patterns differ
103 from those used in their training data. Understanding these differences can help improve speech technology.
104 Twenty university students recorded short texts, producing a set of speech samples that were analyzed using
105 acoustic measurements related to timing, pitch, and loudness. In the first stage of the study, statistical
106 analysis was used to identify which speech characteristics differed consistently between the two dialects. In
107 the second stage, computer models attempted to automatically classify each speech sample according to its
108 dialect. The results showed that differences in speech rhythm, especially how often speakers pause and how
109 variable those pauses are, were the strongest indicators of dialect identity. Voice quality patterns also
110 contributed to classification, while pitch differences played a smaller role. The computer models
111 successfully identified the dialect in most cases, showing that regional speech patterns can be reliably
112 detected. These findings help improve speech technologies and contribute to documenting regional varieties
113 of Brazilian Portuguese.
114

115 **Introduction**

116

117 Regional speech variation constitutes a central dimension of linguistic identity, reflecting regional,
118 social, and interactional histories embedded in speech production. Language varieties (and their
119 regional dialects) are not only differentiated by segmental patterns but also by prosodic
120 organization, including rhythmic structuring, pitch variation, and intensity distribution. These
121 prosodic-acoustic dimensions, in interaction with segmental features and intonational contour
122 patterns, operate as socially meaningful cues, indexing regional belonging and contributing to
123 listeners' perception of dialectal identity. While human listeners are highly sensitive to such
124 variation, Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems frequently struggle to accommodate
125 dialectal diversity, particularly when acoustic models underrepresent structured sociophonetic
126 variability (Braid, 2003; Behravan, 2016; Flege, 1995; Kumar; Singh, 2019; Moyer, 2013).
127

128

129 Recent research in speech technology has shown that performance disparities in ASR systems often
130 reflect insufficient modeling of acoustic-prosodic variation rather than random noise in the speech
131 signal (Wassink; Gansen; Bartholomew, 2022). Temporal organization, intonation dynamics, and
132 voice quality settings may systematically differ across regional varieties, influencing classification
133 accuracy and recognition robustness. Despite these developments, inland Brazilian dialects remain
134 comparatively underrepresented in dialect-sensitive ASR research. This gap motivates the present
135 study, which investigates two inland Brazilian Portuguese varieties: Paraíba (PB) and São Paulo
136 (SP).

136

137 In this pilot study, we hypothesize that prosodic-acoustic descriptors based on duration,

138 fundamental frequency (f0), intensity, and voice quality measures derived from long-term spectral
139 analysis constitute structured acoustic markers distinguishing inland PB and SP dialects of
140 Brazilian Portuguese. A secondary hypothesis holds that these same features provide sufficient
141 discriminative information for automatic dialect classification, with feature-importance analyses
142 expected to reveal a hierarchical contribution of acoustic parameters.

143

144 This study addresses the following research questions (RQ):

- 145 • RQ1. Do prosodic-acoustic descriptors of duration, f0, intensity, and long-term spectral
146 voice quality provide robust and reliable cues for distinguishing the inland Brazilian
147 Portuguese dialects PB and SP?
- 148 • RQ2. To what extent can automatic dialect classification be explained by the relative
149 contribution of prosodic-acoustic features, and how do these features affect ASR
150 performance?

151

152 This paper is structured as follows. Section 1 presents the theoretical framework, situating the study
153 within sociophonetic research and dialect-aware ASR modeling. Section 2 details the methodology,
154 including participants, corpus design, acoustic extraction procedures, statistical modeling, and
155 machine learning (ML) implementation. Section 3 reports the inferential and classification results.
156 Section 4 discusses the findings in relation to research questions and existing literature. The final
157 sections present the conclusion, limitations, and directions for the continuation of the present
158 research.

159

160 **1. Theoretical Framework: Prosody, sociophonetic variation, and ASR systems**

161

162 Recent research has consistently shown that, despite significant technological advances, ASR
163 systems remain sensitive to dialectal and sociophonetic variation. Rather than reflecting random
164 noise in speech signals, recognition errors often stem from the underrepresentation of socially
165 structured acoustic patterns in acoustic model training (Wassink; Gansen; Bartholomew, 2022).
166 Drawing on the variationist tradition, Wassink, Gansen and Bartholomew (2022) argue that
167 linguistic variables, realized through fine-grained segmental and prosodic differences, are
168 conditioned by regional and social factors. However, such sociophonetic knowledge has rarely

169 been fully integrated into ASR architecture.

170

171 A central claim of Wassink, Gansen and Bartholomew (2022) is that dialect-related recognition
172 failures arise primarily at the level of acoustic modeling rather than language modeling. While
173 language models may accommodate non-standard lexical or syntactic patterns, acoustic models are
174 directly dependent on phonetic realization, including vowel quality, rhythmic timing, pitch
175 dynamics, and spectral structure. Importantly, dialects are not treated as discrete, homogeneous
176 entities; instead, recognition errors emerge from clusters of co-occurring acoustic features that may
177 overlap across social and regional boundaries. From this perspective, dialect differentiation is
178 gradient and configuration-based, and ASR failures reflect insufficient modeling of these
179 structured acoustic repertoires.

180

181 This sociophonetic account is further reinforced by Torgbi et al. (2025), who examined the
182 performance of OpenAI’s Whisper large-v3 model on Scottish regional dialects within public
183 service contexts. Their results show that, despite being trained on extensive multilingual and multi-
184 domain datasets, the out-of-the-box model exhibits significantly higher word error rates for
185 regionally accented speech. These findings challenge the assumption that training scale alone
186 ensures dialectal robustness. The authors further demonstrate that fine-tuning the model on region-
187 specific datasets leads to consistent reductions in recognition errors, indicating that dialect-
188 sensitive phonetic and prosodic configurations can be effectively internalized when adequately
189 represented in acoustic modeling. Moreover, their analysis highlights that performance disparities
190 are not merely technical artifacts but reflect asymmetries in the sociolinguistic distribution of
191 training data. Both works – Wassink, Gansen and Bartholomew (2022) and Torgbi et al. (2025) –
192 converge on the view that dialectal variability must be explicitly modeled at the acoustic level and
193 that persistent ASR performance gaps are rooted in structured sociophonetic underrepresentation
194 rather than in random variation.

195

196 In addition to the studies discussed above, Koenecke et al. (2020) examined the ability of five state-
197 of-the-art commercial ASR systems — developed by Amazon, Apple, Google, IBM, and Microsoft
198 — to transcribe structured sociolinguistic interviews with 42 speakers of General American (GA)
199 English and 73 African American Vernacular English (AAVE) speakers, finding that all five

200 systems exhibited substantial racial disparities, with an average word error rate of 0.35 for AAVE
201 speakers compared with 0.19 for GA speakers. The authors trace these disparities directly to the
202 underlying acoustic models, demonstrating that the performance gap was equally large on a
203 matched subset of identical phrases produced by speakers of both groups, which points to the
204 phonological, phonetic, and prosodic characteristics of AAVE as the primary drivers of recognition
205 failure rather than lexical or grammatical features. Earlier work by Tatman (2017) had already
206 identified similar patterns: an evaluation of YouTube's automatically-generated captions across
207 two genders and five dialect groups demonstrated robust differences in accuracy across both gender
208 and dialect, with systematically lower performance for speakers from Scotland — one of the
209 earliest empirical demonstrations of the relationship between regional speech variety and ASR
210 performance disparities. These findings were further extended by Tatman and Kasten (2017), who
211 compared the accuracy of Bing Speech and YouTube captions across gender, race, and four dialects
212 of American English, finding that the lowest average error rates consistently corresponded to GA
213 speakers.

214

215 Markl (2022) investigated the performance of Google and Amazon transcription services across
216 multiple accents of British English and found that both systems perform substantially worse for L2
217 speakers and for speakers of stigmatized regional varieties of British English, exploring the
218 structural and sociopolitical mechanisms through which speech and language technologies
219 reproduce disadvantage for marginalized language communities. Expanding the scope further,
220 Chan et al. (2022) evaluated the effectiveness of automatic captioning for world English varieties,
221 comparing word error rates across English varieties supported and unsupported by a major
222 commercial ASR provider, and finding that English varieties classified as supported consistently
223 yield lower error rates, while unsupported varieties — including those typologically distant from
224 the training data — exhibit systematically higher error rates.

225

226 These studies establish a robust and cross-linguistically consistent pattern: ASR performance
227 disparities correlate with the acoustic distance between a speaker's variety and the dominant variety
228 in the training corpus, and this distance is structured sociophonetically, reflecting systematic
229 sources of phonetic variation that have yet to be adequately represented in acoustic model
230 architectures, rather than being a product of random variation or recording conditions.

231 A systematic review of 100 studies on speech synthesis (Galdino et al., 2025) reveals that f0 is by
232 far the most extensively modeled prosodic dimension across text-to-speech systems, present in 95
233 of the 100 studies surveyed, with duration and intensity following as secondary but consistently
234 correlates. However, the review also demonstrates that the relative weighting and
235 operationalization of these parameters vary substantially across systems, languages, and
236 applications: f0 dominates in synthesis architectures optimized for perceived naturalness and
237 intonational expressiveness, while duration and intensity receive proportionally greater emphasis
238 in rhythm-sensitive and prominence-driven contexts. These results indicate that while f0, duration,
239 and intensity collectively define the parameter space of prosodic modeling, the internal hierarchy
240 among them, that is, which dimension carries the greatest explanatory weight, is neither fixed nor
241 universal across linguistic and dialectal contexts. This observation directly motivates the present
242 investigation: rather than assuming a predetermined hierarchy derived from synthesis research, this
243 study empirically examines how duration, f0, and intensity are hierarchically organized in the
244 specific context of two inland Brazilian Portuguese dialect varieties. Importantly, the review also
245 shows that research in this area remains strongly concentrated in a small set of languages —
246 particularly English, Mandarin, and Japanese — while many languages and regional varieties
247 remain comparatively underexplored. In this sense, extending prosodic-acoustic investigation to
248 underrepresented varieties of Brazilian Portuguese contributes not only to sociophonetic
249 description but also to the broader development of speech technologies capable of modeling
250 prosodic variability across diverse linguistic contexts.

251

252 These perspectives directly motivate investigations of regional variation within Brazilian
253 Portuguese. Studies such as Constantini and Barbosa (2015) posit that Brazilian Portuguese
254 exhibits strong prosodic and rhythmic diversity across regions, yet inland varieties remain
255 comparatively underrepresented in speech technology research. The authors investigated the role
256 of prosodic-acoustic parameters in distinguishing regional varieties in seven Brazilian Portuguese
257 dialects and analyzed a set of prosodic descriptors including speech rate, duration variability of
258 vowel-to-vowel units, spectral emphasis, and f0 median. Their statistical analyses revealed
259 significant differences across varieties for parameters related to intensity, pitch, and rhythmic
260 structure, demonstrating that prosody can function as a reliable indicator of dialectal variation.
261 Their research shows that prosodic cues such as duration variability and spectral emphasis can

262 separate regional groupings within Brazilian Portuguese, confirming the view that dialectal identity
263 is reflected not only in segmental features but also in systematic suprasegmental (i.e., prosodic)
264 organization.

265

266 More recent research on Brazilian prosody has demonstrated that prosodic parameters, such as
267 duration and f0 contours, function as stable markers of Brazilian Portuguese (Barbosa; Alvarenga,
268 2024). In addition, Silveira, Albert and Grice (2025) compare the prosodic configuration of
269 Alagoas and São Paulo dialectal varieties, focusing on f0 dynamics in boundary contexts. Using
270 measures of f0 slope and intrasyllabic synchrony, the study identifies systematic regional
271 differences in pitch excursion and contour direction, particularly at terminal and non-terminal
272 boundaries. The results demonstrate that dialect differentiation is encoded in both continuous and
273 categorical intonational patterns, reinforcing the role of prosodic-acoustic features as stable
274 markers of regional identity.

275

276 With respect to automatic dialect recognition, regional speech variation can be systematically
277 modeled through acoustic feature extraction and statistical classification techniques. In the context
278 of Brazilian Portuguese, studies combining speech signal processing and ML have shown that
279 dialect identification can be approached as a pattern recognition problem in which acoustic
280 representations capture structured phonetic and prosodic variability across regions. For instance,
281 Batista (2019) investigates Brazilian regional accent identification in a sentence-reading task using
282 statistical modeling techniques such as Gaussian Mixture Models, iVectors, and Support Vector
283 Machines, demonstrating that dialectal variation can be computationally modeled through acoustic
284 descriptors derived from the speech signal. Importantly, this line of research emphasizes that
285 regional dialects do not represent random deviations but structured linguistic patterns that can be
286 detected through systematic acoustic analysis.

287

288 This perspective aligns with recent computational studies showing that prosodic-acoustic
289 information can be reliably extracted and operationalized in speech technology. Craveiro et al.
290 (2024), for example, demonstrate that ML classifiers using prosodic-acoustic features can
291 automatically segment prosodic units, highlighting the feasibility of extracting rhythmic and
292 intonational patterns through automated methods. Similarly, Gauy and Finger (2023) show that

293 transformer-based acoustic models pre-trained on Brazilian Portuguese corpora capture subtle
294 acoustic variability, improving downstream classification tasks. Together, these studies reinforce
295 the view that prosodic-acoustic features constitute a computationally tractable dimension of dialect
296 variation and provide a foundation for dialect-sensitive ASR modeling.

297

298 The selection of prosodic-acoustic parameters in this study was guided by three complementary
299 criteria. First, the literature reviewed above establishes that duration, f0, and intensity — together
300 with voice quality measures derived from long-term spectral analysis — constitute the principal
301 acoustic correlates of prosodic organization, and their role in dialect differentiation has been
302 documented in Brazilian Portuguese (Constantini; Barbosa, 2015; Barbosa; Alvarenga, 2024).
303 Second, these dimensions correspond precisely to the parameters covered by the third step of
304 *Protosody* protocol, which is the *SpeechRhythmExtractor* pipeline (Silva Jr.; Barbosa; Monte,
305 2024), adopted here for methodological consistency and reproducibility. Third, within each
306 dimension, the specific measures extracted — pause-based duration measures, spectral tilt, f0
307 variability and contour slope — were selected because they have been shown to capture supra-
308 segmental and phonatory properties sensitive to regional variation. The set was constrained,
309 consistent with the pilot scope, to ensure statistical stability given the 20-speaker sample.
310 Additional features are identified as a priority for future research in Section 8.

311

312 Considering the use of prosodic-acoustic differentiation within a machine-learning framework, this
313 study integrates sociophonetic analysis with ML-based ASR research to investigate inland
314 Brazilian dialects that remain underrepresented in speech corpora. In doing so, it follows the
315 research agenda proposed by Wassink, Gansen and Bartholomew (2022) by examining, in a
316 Brazilian context, how systematic prosodic variability affects dialect-sensitive ASR modeling.

317

318 **2. Methodology 1: corpus design, acoustic procedures, and statistical analysis**

319

320 **2.1.Participants**

321

322 The study included 20 undergraduate students enrolled in Letras (Modern Languages) programs,
323 with ten participants from the State University of Paraíba (UEPB) and ten from the State University

324 of São Paulo (UNESP). The sample was balanced for gender (50% female, 50% male). Participants
325 were between 18 and 23 years old ($M = 20.2$; $SD = 2.70$). All participants were native speakers of
326 Brazilian Portuguese and were born and raised in inland municipalities of their respective states.
327 The Paraíba group consisted of students from Guarabira and surrounding cities, representing the
328 regional speech variety commonly referred to as Brejo Paraibano (*the Paraiban Brejo*) speech. The
329 São Paulo group comprised students from São José do Rio Preto and neighboring municipalities,
330 representing the inland São Paulo variety. Initial contact with participants occurred at the beginning
331 of the academic semester, when they were enrolled in the course “Fonética e Fonologia” at both
332 institutions. Recruitment procedures were conducted simultaneously at UEPB and UNESP to
333 ensure comparable academic and instructional contexts across groups.

334

335 **2.2.Data Collection**

336

337 The corpus analyzed in this study was derived from controlled reading tasks based on a scripted
338 text prepared for a podcast in Brazilian Portuguese. The podcast addressed topics in phonetics,
339 phonology, and the potential influence of sociophonetic differences between the PB and SP dialects
340 on foreign language speech. The recording process took approximately two weeks, generating
341 about 1 hour and 30 minutes of audio material. For analytical purposes, each recording was
342 segmented into 23 speech stretches, resulting in an initial dataset of 460 speech samples. Sample
343 balance was controlled across dialect groups, yielding exactly 230 samples for PB and 230 samples
344 for SP.

345

346 Participants received the text scripts and were instructed to read them at a natural speaking rate,
347 using their everyday speaking voice — that is, the habitual vocal quality they employ in ordinary
348 conversational contexts — without artificially raising or lowering their pitch, breathiness, or
349 loudness — provided they felt familiar with the content. This procedure follows recommendations
350 for elicited speech protocols designed to minimize hyperarticulation and prosodic distortion
351 associated with reading tasks (cf. Silva Jr.; Barbosa, 2023). Participants were allowed to rehearse
352 the text, silently or aloud, for as long as needed before the recording session.

353

354 Data collection was conducted remotely using voice recording applications installed on

355 participants’ personal mobile phones. Recordings were saved in uncompressed “.wav” format to
 356 preserve acoustic quality. Given the remote recording context, participants received detailed
 357 guidelines to minimize environmental noise and ensure acoustic consistency. These guidelines
 358 included selecting quiet recording environments, positioning themselves near sound-attenuating
 359 surfaces (e.g., curtains or upholstered furniture), maintaining a consistent microphone-to-mouth
 360 distance of approximately 10–15 cm, and avoiding excessive background reverberation. These
 361 procedures were adopted in accordance with best practices for remote acoustic data collection (e.g.,
 362 Zhang et al., 2021). Table 1 provides a synthesis of data collection procedures.

363

Dialect	Participants (per dialect)	<i>N</i>	Samples (per dialect)	<i>N</i>	Recordings	Rendition
PB	10	20	230	460	Controlled reading from text scripts of a Podcast	~1h 30m
SP	10		230			

364 **Table 1:** Data collection synthesis. Dialect (PB or SP); Number of participants per dialect and the total (*N*);
 365 Speech samples per dialect and the total (*N*); recording task that originated the speech samples; the
 366 approximate (~) whole recording time (Rendition).
 367

368 2.3. Acoustic Analysis

369

370 Acoustic processing was conducted using Praat (Boersma; Weenink, 2024), following the
 371 segmentation and feature-extraction guidelines proposed by Silva Jr., Barbosa and Monte (2024),
 372 and Silva Jr. and Barbosa (2024). The procedure consists of three sequential stages: (i) phonetic
 373 forced alignment, (ii) realignment and relabeling of phonetic units, and (iii) automatic extraction
 374 of prosodic-acoustic parameters. This pipeline ensures segmentation consistency, phonetic
 375 accuracy, and replicable feature computation across recordings.

376

377 2.3.1. Step 1: Phonetic forced alignment

378

379 Automatic phonetic alignment was performed using the MAUS (Munich Automatic Segmentation)
 380 aligner (Kisler et al., 2017) via its web-based interface. Each pair of sound and orthographic
 381 transcription files (with identical filenames) was submitted for processing. For each audio file, the
 382 aligner generated a corresponding TextGrid file compatible with Praat. These files contained time-
 383 aligned phonetic segment boundaries, serving as the basis for subsequent refinement and feature
 384 extraction.

385 2.3.2. Step 2: Realignment, relabeling, and manual correction

386

387 Following forced alignment in step 1, a script for Praat was employed to implement new segment
388 boundaries and reorganize annotation tiers according to vowel-to-vowel-based rhythmic units. This
389 step ensured consistency in the definition of phonetic units and facilitated the extraction of prosodic
390 measures. The resulting annotation structure comprised the following tiers:

391

- 392 • Tier 1 (V_to_V units): Phonetic syllable units spanning from the onset of one vowel to the
393 onset of the subsequent vowel (Barbosa, 2006).
- 394 • Tier 2: Segmental classification, including vowels (V), consonants (C), and silent or filled
395 pauses (#).
- 396 • Tier 3: Speech chunks (CH), corresponding to automatically segmented stretches based on
397 pause duration and intensity, a heuristic-based method to detect prosodic boundaries
398 proposed by Craveiro et al. (2024). This chunk segmentation was later used for statistical
399 and automatic classification procedures.

400

401 Following automatic forced alignment procedures, all TextGrid annotations were manually
402 inspected and corrected by an experienced phonetician. This step was necessary to ensure the
403 consistency and reliability of phonetic segmentation, as automatic alignment tools may introduce
404 inaccuracies, particularly in cases involving coarticulation, segment reduction, or low signal
405 quality. As emphasized by Ladefoged (2003), acoustic measurements obtained through
406 computational methods are not free from error, and careful manual verification is often required to
407 ensure analytical precision.

408

409 Manual correction was carried out through the joint analysis of waveform and wide-band
410 spectrogram displays, following the criteria proposed by Barbosa and Madureira (2015). Vowel
411 boundaries were established based on the presence of periodic waveform patterns and stable
412 formant structures, particularly the first (f1) and second (f2) formants, which are central to vowel
413 quality and identity. Consonantal segments were evaluated according to their characteristic
414 acoustic properties. Stops were identified by a closure interval (silence), the possible presence of a
415 voicing bar in voiced contexts, a burst release, and the transition into the following vowel.
416 Fricatives were defined by sustained aperiodic noise, with voicing distinctions determined by the
417 presence or absence of a voicing bar. Laterals and nasals were identified by periodic waveforms of
418 lower amplitude than vowels, a concentration of energy in lower frequencies, and the presence of

419 antiresonances. Trills and taps were characterized by brief interruptions in the waveform caused
420 by rapid articulatory contact.

421

422 In addition, speech chunks were identified by linguistic and acoustic-phonetic criteria to ensure the
423 integrity of the input features. Linguistically, chunks were delimited based on prosodic envelopes
424 (i.e., variations in amplitude, duration, and f_0 that shape the speech signal acting as cues for
425 perception and comprehension), ensuring that boundaries coincide with natural prosodic breaks to
426 preserve the integrity of the syllable structures or rhythmic units (Barbosa, 2006; Cantoni et al.,
427 2022). This prevented the fragmentation of phonotactic units, such as complex onsets or diphthongs
428 which could introduce spectral artifacts (i.e., distortions or noise that appear in the spectrogram but
429 were not actually produced by the speaker's vocal tract) into the machine learning model. All
430 corrections were applied conservatively, prioritizing clear acoustic evidence and avoiding
431 unnecessary over-segmentation.

432

433 **2.3.3. Step 3: Automatic Feature Extraction**

434

435 Prosodic-acoustic parameters based on f_0 , duration, and intensity were automatically extracted
436 using the *SpeechRhythmExtractor* script for Praat (Silva Jr., 2026; Silva Jr.; Barbosa; Monte, 2024).
437 This script computes measures from the segmented tiers defined in Step 2 (Section 2.3.2) at the
438 level of individual V-to-V units and speech chunks. F_0 measures were computed locally, within
439 each speech chunk. Rising f_0 slope (df_0mean_pos) was operationalized as the mean rate of f_0
440 change (in semitones per second) over intervals in which the contour displays a positive first
441 derivative — that is, rising movements detected locally within each unit. The standard deviation of
442 the rising slope (df_0sd_pos) captures variability in those local rising movements within a chunk.
443 F_0 standard deviation (f_0sd) and semi-interquartile range (f_0SAQ) were computed across all voiced
444 frames within each chunk, reflecting overall pitch dispersion. These local values were aggregated
445 at the speaker level using the mean, ensuring comparability across speakers. Intensity measures
446 included the spectral tilt parameter (sl_LTAS_alpha), derived from the slope of the long-term
447 average spectrum (LTAS) in the low-frequency domain — an index of phonatory mode and voice
448 quality rather than loudness per se — and the variation coefficient of intensity ($cvint$), computed
449 as the standard deviation of intensity normalized by its mean, reflecting short-term amplitude

450 fluctuations. Duration measures comprised pause standard deviation (*pause_sd*), mean pause
451 duration (*pause_meandur*), and pause rate (*pause_rate*, i.e., number of pauses per second of
452 speech). All measures were computed within the chunk tier (Tier 3), ensuring that each observation
453 corresponds to a delimited prosodic unit.

454

455 **2.4.Data Screening Procedures**

456

457 Prior to statistical and computational modeling, the dataset was screened for extreme values, zero
458 values, and potential artifacts arising from acoustic extraction and segmentation procedures. Such
459 values are commonly observed in automatically extracted prosodic-acoustic datasets and may
460 reflect both linguistically meaningful variation and methodological constraints inherent to speech
461 signal processing (e.g., Boersma; Weenink, 2024; Hirst, 2011; Kisler et al., 2017; Rybka; Janicki,
462 2013; Galdino et al., 2025).

463

464 Extreme values were manually inspected to determine whether they corresponded to plausible
465 speech behavior (e.g., extended pauses, high pitch excursions, or increased intensity variability) or
466 to extraction anomalies. No observations were removed solely based on magnitude. Instead, values
467 were retained when consistent with known patterns of natural prosodic variability, in line with
468 recommendations emphasizing ecological validity in speech analysis (Barbosa, 2006). Zero values
469 were treated with particular care. In prosodic-acoustic datasets, zero values may arise from at least
470 three sources:

- 471 i. The absence of meaningful variation in the measured phenomenon — for instance,
472 *pause_sd* approaches zero when all pauses within a chunk are of near-identical duration, a
473 condition that may arise in short or highly controlled speech stretches; it is important to
474 note, however, that zero values for *pause_rate* are not expected in this dataset, since the
475 chunk segmentation algorithm (Step 2, section 2.3.2) requires the simultaneous presence of
476 a silent interval of at least 35 ms and an intensity threshold of at least 40 dB for a chunk
477 boundary to be established (cf. Akis; Bell; Simpson, 2025; Silva Jr.; Barbosa; Monte, 2024;
478 among other Voice Activity Detection studies), meaning that every segmented chunk
479 contains at least one pause event by construction.
- 480 ii. Minimal acoustic variation (e.g., flat or near-monotonic f0 contours yielding near-zero

481 slope values).
482 iii. Methodological and signal-processing constraints inherent to automatic feature extraction,
483 particularly in unvoiced segments, low-intensity intervals, or short analysis windows.
484 Notably, within standard extraction frameworks such as in The Geneva Minimalistic
485 Acoustic Parameter Set (GeMAPS - Eyben et al., 2016), f_0 is explicitly defined as zero in
486 unvoiced regions, reflecting the absence of periodic vocal fold vibration rather than an error
487 in processing (Boersma; Weenink, 2024; Hirst, 2011; Kisler et al., 2017).

488

489 In addition, the inclusion of zero and near-zero values aligns with a usage-based and gradient
490 perspective on prosodic variation, in which the absence of certain acoustic events (e.g., pauses or
491 pitch movement) is itself informative for modeling prosodic organization. Therefore, the adopted
492 data screening procedures prioritized interpretability and ecological validity over aggressive
493 filtering, ensuring that the resulting dataset preserves the full range of prosodic-acoustic variation
494 relevant for both inferential and predictive analyses (James et al., 2013; Molnar, 2022).

495

496 **2.5. Statistical Analysis**

497

498 For the statistical analysis, Linear Mixed-Effects Models (LMEM) were employed. This modeling
499 approach has demonstrated robustness and flexibility in recent research involving
500 multidimensional comparisons of prosodic-acoustic parameters across different speaker groups,
501 including both L1 and L2 populations (cf. Ortega-Llebaria; Silva Jr.; Nagao, 2023; Silva Jr.; Silva;
502 Meer, 2024; Teixeira, 2023). By incorporating both fixed effects (dialect) and random effects
503 (participant), LMEM enables reliable estimation of dialect-related differences while controlling for
504 individual variability, thereby reducing the risk of Type I Error (Barr et al., 2013; Baayen;
505 Davidson; Bates, 2008).

506

507 Furthermore, this modeling framework is especially well-suited for dialect classification and
508 speech research, as it allows for the identification and quantification of specific prosodic-acoustic
509 features that significantly contribute to cross-dialect differentiation, while simultaneously
510 accounting for natural inter-speaker variability (Baayen; Davidson; Bates, 2008; Wieling; Tiede;
511 Tomaschek, 2017). Mixed-effects models explicitly model hierarchical and grouped speech data,

512 enabling more accurate estimation of dialect effects while preserving the structure of speaker-
513 dependent variability.

514

515 This approach provides robustness for evaluating which acoustic parameters function as reliable
516 predictors in automatic dialect classification and for interpreting their contribution to ASR-related
517 performance, as mixed-effects models are specifically designed to handle correlated and
518 hierarchical data structures commonly found in speech corpora (Nakagawa; Schielzeth, 2013; Barr
519 et al., 2013).

520

521 In addition to statistical robustness, the explanatory power of the models was assessed using the
522 coefficient of determination (R^2), calculated as marginal R^2 and conditional R^2 , following the
523 framework proposed by Nakagawa and Schielzeth (2013). Marginal R^2 represents the proportion
524 of variance explained exclusively by fixed effects (i.e., dialect “PB-SP”, where “PB” is the
525 reference level), whereas conditional R^2 reflects the total variance explained by both fixed and
526 random effects (i.e., dialect and inter-speaker variability). This distinction is particularly relevant
527 in speech research, where inter-speaker variability constitutes an inherent and meaningful source
528 of acoustic variation.

529

530 The interpretation of R^2 values remains a subject of discussion in the statistical literature. To ensure
531 consistent and theoretically grounded interpretation, this study adopted the normalization
532 procedures proposed by Silva Jr. and Barbosa (2023), that integrate effect-size benchmarks from
533 Cohen (1992), Chin (1998), Henseler; Ringle; Sinkovics (2009), and Moksony (1999). Based on
534 these procedures, effect sizes were interpreted according to the following criteria:

- 535 • Strong effect size: $R^2 \geq 0.50$
- 536 • Weak-to-satisfactory effect size: $0.21 \leq R^2 \leq 0.49$
- 537 • Weak effect size: $R^2 \leq 0.20$

538

539 A significance alpha level of 5% was established, meaning that observed differences were
540 considered statistically significant if the probability (p-value) was less than or equal 0.05 ($p \leq 0.05$).

541 The statistical analysis was performed within the R environment/language (R Core Team, 2026).

542

543

544 **3. Results 1: statistical modeling**

545

546 This section reports the prosodic-acoustic parameters that showed statistically significant dialect
 547 differences, along with their contribution to automatic dialect classification.

548

549 Linear mixed-effects models were fitted for each prosodic-acoustic parameter, with ‘Dialect’ as a
 550 fixed effect and ‘Speaker’ as the random intercept. Effect sizes are reported as marginal R²
 551 (variance explained by fixed effects) and conditional R² (variance explained by fixed and random
 552 effects combined) in accordance with Nakagawa and Schielzeth (2013). Table 2 and Figure 1
 553 synthesize the results for all acoustic features.

554

Acoustic correlate	Prosodic feature	β	SE	$t(18)$	p	R ²	
						m	c
f0	<i>f0sd</i>	0.535	0.249	2.15	=0.04	0.03	0.12
	<i>f0SAQ</i>	0.465	0.203	2.29	=0.03	0.02	0.07
	<i>df0mean_pos</i>	1.975	0.694	2.85	=0.01	0.05	0.12
	<i>df0sd_pos</i>	1.076	0.485	2.22	=0.04	0.03	0.11
Intensity	<i>sl_LTAS_alpha</i>	5.230	0.582	8.98	<0.001	0.27	0.31
	<i>cvint</i>	-10.701	2.986	-3.58	<0.001	0.03	0.03
Duration	<i>Pause SD</i>	581.81	97.29	5.98	<0.001	0.44	0.68
	<i>Pause mean</i>	176.82	82.97	2.13	=0.04	0.10	0.54
	<i>Pause rate</i>	0.14	0.055	2.54	=0.02	0.14	0.56

555 **Table 2:** Prosodic-acoustic correlate, prosodic-acoustic features for each correlate, estimate coefficients of
 556 the models (β), standard error (SE) values, t -value (degrees of freedom from the fixed effects), p -value, and
 557 the coefficients of determination (R²) of the fixed effects (marginal – m) and the combined fixed + random
 558 effects (conditional – c).
 559

560 Across all models ($N = 460$ speech; $N = 20$ speakers), dialect significantly affected every prosodic-
 561 acoustic parameter analyzed in this section.

Figure 1: Boxplots of the statistically significant acoustic parameters based on the Mixed-Effects statistics. Nine acoustic parameters related to f0: **f0 standard deviation (SD)** – *f0sd*; **f0 semi-interquartile range (semi-IQR)** – *f0SAQ*; **rising f0 slope** – *df0mean_pos*; **rising f0 SD slope** – *df0sd_pos* (panels A-D). Intensity: **spectral tilt (voice quality)** – *sl_LTAS_alpha*; **intensity variation coefficient** – *cvint* (panels E, F). Duration: **pause SD** – *pause_sd*; **pause duration mean** – *pause_meandur*; **pause rate** (pauses per second) – *pause_rate* (panels G-I) controlled for two dialects (PB, SP).

ALT – Figure 1: Boxplots comparing PB and SP dialects across nine prosodic-acoustic parameters related to pitch, intensity, and pause timing. The plots show generally higher pause-related values and intensity variation in SP compared to PB, indicating dialectal differences in rhythmic and voice-quality patterns.

3.1. Fundamental frequency (f0)

With respect to f0 measures, dialect exerted a consistent, though generally weak-to-satisfactory, effect across variability and contour-related parameters. f0 standard deviation (*f0sd*, Figure 1A) differed significantly between dialects ($\beta = 0.535$, $SE = 0.249$, $t(18) = 2.15$, $p = .04$), with SP speakers displaying greater pitch variability. However, the marginal (*m*) R^2 was 0.03 and the conditional (*c*) R^2 reached 0.12, indicating that dialect accounted for a relatively small portion of the total variance in f0 dispersion. A similar pattern emerged for the semi-amplitude interquartile range (i.e., semi-IQR) (*f0SAQ*, Figure 1B), which was also significantly higher in the SP group ($\beta = 0.465$, $SE = 0.203$, $t(18) = 2.29$, $p = .03$). Nonetheless, effect sizes remained small ($R^2_m = 0.02$; $R^2_c = 0.07$), suggesting limited explanatory strength.

Contour dynamics revealed comparable tendencies. The mean f0 rising slope (*df0mean_pos*, Figure

586 1C) was significantly greater in the SP dialect ($\beta = 1.975$, $SE = 0.694$, $t(18) = 2.85$, $p = .01$),
587 although the R^2m and R^2c values (0.05 and 0.12, respectively) also indicate a weak explanatory
588 power. Likewise, the standard deviation of the f0 rising slope (*df0sd_pos*, Figure 1D), which
589 captures the dispersion of rising contour movements, showed a significant dialect effect ($\beta = 1.076$,
590 $SE = 0.485$, $t(18) = 2.22$, $p = .04$), but with weak R^2m (.03) and R^2c (0.11).

591

592 Taken together, these findings suggest that while the two dialects differ systematically in pitch
593 variability and contour dynamics, particularly with SP speakers exhibiting greater dispersion and
594 steeper rising movements, f0-based measures contribute relatively modest proportions of explained
595 variance. Although pitch dynamics participate in dialect differentiation, they appear to function as
596 secondary cues rather than primary discriminators in the present data.

597

598 **3.2.Intensity**

599

600 It is important to note at the outset that the two intensity-related parameters in this study tap into
601 distinct phonatory phenomena and should not be conflated under a single interpretation of
602 "intensity." The spectral tilt parameter (*sl_LTAS_alpha*) reflects differences in phonation mode —
603 specifically, the distribution of vocal energy across the frequency spectrum as captured by the
604 LTAS slope in the low-frequency domain — and is best understood as a voice quality index rather
605 than a measure of loudness per se (Esling; Edmondson, 2011; Garellek, 2022). The variation
606 coefficient of intensity (*cvint*), by contrast, captures short-term fluctuations in the amplitude
607 envelope and is more directly related to differences in loudness variability across the speech signal,
608 reflecting how consistently or variably speakers modulate their overall vocal effort. This distinction
609 is essential for the correct interpretation of the results that follow.

610

611 Intensity-based measures revealed a markedly stronger dialect effect, particularly in long-term
612 spectral configuration. Spectral tilt in the low-frequency domain (*sl_LTAS_alpha*, Figure 1E),
613 which is related to vocal effort, was robustly predicted by dialect ($\beta = 5.230$, $SE = 0.582$, $t(18) =$
614 8.98 , $p < .001$), with SP speakers exhibiting significantly higher values. The R^2m of 0.27 indicates
615 that dialect alone accounted for 27% of the variance, while the R^2c (0.31) indicates a weak-to-
616 satisfactory effect for the combined fixed and random effects, suggesting that a substantial portion

617 of the total variance is also attributable to speaker-specific variability. This result positions spectral
618 tilt as one of the reliable acoustic markers of dialectal differentiation in the corpus.

619

620 In contrast, the variation coefficient (VC) of intensity (*cvint*, Figure 1F) also reached statistical
621 significance ($\beta = -10.701$, $SE = 2.986$, $t(18) = -3.584$, $p < .001$), with SP speakers showing lower
622 variability. However, both $R^2m|c$ values were 0.03, and the model exhibited a singular fit,
623 indicating that the practical contribution of this parameter is limited and weak despite statistical
624 significance. Nevertheless, *cvint* also contributes as a complementary indicator of dialect-specific
625 loudness variability, capturing differences in how consistently PB and SP speakers modulate
626 amplitude across the speech signal. Its inclusion in the feature set therefore reflects the
627 multidimensional nature of the intensity domain rather than a redundancy with *sl_LTAS_alpha*.

628

629 Overall, the intensity domain demonstrates that dialectal differences are strongly encoded in long-
630 term spectral balance rather than in short-term amplitude variability. It is important to clarify that
631 intensity, as an acoustic dimension, does not carry direct linguistic meaning by itself; rather, its
632 relevance emerges through specific derived measures that tap into distinct phonatory and voice-
633 quality phenomena. Spectral tilt (*sl_LTAS_alpha*) is linked to global phonatory effort and the
634 distribution of vocal energy across frequency bands, reflecting habitual voice quality settings that
635 index regional identity (Esling; Edmondson, 2011; Thomas, 2011). The variation coefficient of
636 intensity (*cvint*), by contrast, captures short-term fluctuations in amplitude, which may reflect
637 differences in prominence signaling and speech rhythm across dialect groups.

638

639 **3.3.Duration**

640

641 Temporal parameters displayed the most substantial dialectal contrasts, particularly in pausing
642 behavior. Pause duration variability (*pause_sd*, Figure 1G) was strongly predicted by dialect ($\beta =$
643 581.81 , $SE = 97.29$, $t(18) = 5.98$, $p < .001$), with SP speakers exhibiting markedly greater
644 dispersion. The R^2m of 0.443 indicates a strong fixed-effect contribution, and the R^2c of 0.676
645 reflects considerable overall explanatory power. This suggests that differences in pause distribution
646 may play a central role in the Brazilian Portuguese inland dialectal distinction presented here.

647

648 Although the current analysis does not permit a precise statement about the syntactic or discourse
649 positions at which pauses occur — given that chunks were defined by prosodic rather than syntactic
650 criteria — the results indicate that SP speakers exhibit not only longer but also more variable
651 pauses, suggesting greater within-speaker inconsistency in pause duration across the utterance.
652 This pattern is consistent with a speech planning profile in which SP speakers distribute silences
653 less uniformly, possibly reflecting differences in discourse pacing or prosodic chunking strategies
654 relative to PB speakers. Whether these pauses cluster at syntactic boundaries, between prosodic
655 phrases, or across other discourse units remains a question for future investigation employing
656 syntactically annotated corpora.

657

658 Mean pause duration (*pause_meandur*, Figure 1H) was also significantly longer in the SP dialect
659 ($\beta = 176.82$, $SE = 82.97$, $t(18) = 2.13$, $p = .04$). Although the R^2m (0.10) indicates a weak direct
660 contribution of dialect, the R^2c (0.54) reveals substantial speaker-related variability. Similarly,
661 pause rate (*pause_rate*, Figure 1I - i.e., pauses per second) differed significantly between dialects
662 ($\beta = 0.141$, $SE = 0.055$, $t(18) = 2.54$, $p = .02$), with SP speakers producing pauses more frequently.
663 The R^2m of 0.14 also suggests a weak fixed-effect contribution, while the R^2c of 0.56 again
664 highlights meaningful inter-speaker differences.

665

666 It should be noted that pause duration variability (*pause_sd*) reflects dispersion in the length of
667 pauses rather than their positional distribution within the utterance. A high *pause_sd* value indicates
668 that a speaker's pauses vary considerably in duration — some very brief, others markedly extended
669 — rather than that pauses occur at syntactic positions. This measure therefore captures a temporal
670 rhythm signature of the dialect, characterizing the degree of rhythmic variability in the speaker's
671 pausing behavior, and is analytically distinct from measures of pause frequency (*pause_rate*) or
672 average duration (*pause_meandur*).

673

674 Collectively, these temporal findings indicate that dialectal differentiation is particularly salient in
675 the organization of speech rhythm and pausing strategies. The magnitude of the effects, especially
676 for pause variability, demonstrates that temporal structuring functions as a primary acoustic
677 dimension of distinction between the dialects. Compared to f_0 measures, duration-related
678 parameters provide substantially greater explanatory power, underscoring the importance of

679 rhythmic organization in capturing dialect-specific prosodic patterns.

680

681 **4. Methodology 2: Automatic dialect classification procedures**

682

683 An automatic accent classification task was implemented using a binary Artificial Intelligence
684 (AI)-based classifier. The system was developed in Python (Van Rossum; Drake, 2009) and
685 designed to classify speech samples according to dialect origin, identifying whether a given
686 recording belonged to the Paraíba inland dialect (PB) or the São Paulo inland dialect (SP). The
687 classification was based exclusively on prosodic-acoustic features extracted from each
688 participant's speech. For the purposes of this pilot study, the ML models were trained only on the
689 subset of acoustic parameters that showed statistical significance in the LMEM (Table 2, section
690 3), ensuring methodological consistency between the inferential and predictive stages of the
691 analysis.

692

693 Six ML techniques were implemented and compared to one another using Accuracy and Error Rate
694 (ER) as performance metrics. The six classifiers are not treated as competing alternatives in a
695 model-selection sense; rather, they are implemented as complementary analytical lenses that differ
696 in their decision mechanisms. By comparing their outputs, this stage evaluates whether the
697 prosodic-acoustic hierarchy identified in the inferential phase is robust across distinct algorithmic
698 approaches, from linear (LDA) to non-linear ensemble methods (RF, GBM).

699 These techniques (cf. section 4.1-4.6) differ in how they model relationships between acoustic
700 variables and dialect categories, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of how prosodic-
701 acoustic features contribute to automatic dialect classification (Jassim; Abdulmohsin, 2025; James
702 et al., 2013; Nielsen, 2021; Silva et al., 2023; Silva Jr.; Barbosa, 2022).

703

704 **4.1.Random Forest (RF)**

705

706 Random Forest is an ensemble learning technique that combines multiple Decision Trees to
707 produce a single classification outcome. Each tree is trained using a random subset of acoustic
708 observations and acoustic variables, and the final classification is determined through a majority
709 voting procedure. This structure reduces overfitting and increases model robustness, particularly

710 in speech datasets where acoustic variables may be correlated. In the context of dialect
711 classification proposed in this study (and based on Table 2), Random Forest evaluates how
712 combinations of prosodic-acoustic features - such as pause descriptors, spectral tilt, variation
713 coefficient (VC) of intensity, and pitch variability - jointly contribute to distinguishing PB and SP
714 speakers. Because each tree may prioritize different acoustic features or speakers, the model
715 captures both consistent dialect patterns and natural inter-speaker variability. This makes Random
716 Forest particularly suitable for identifying complex, multidimensional acoustic patterns associated
717 with dialect-specific prosodic organization.

718

719 **4.2. Decision Tree (DT)**

720

721 Decision Trees classify data by recursively splitting observations according to decision rules based
722 on acoustic feature values. Each split selects the acoustic parameter that best separates the dialect
723 groups, based on statistical criteria such as entropy or the Gini index. This model provides a
724 transparent representation of dialect differentiation, as it explicitly reveals which acoustic
725 variables, and which thresholds, most effectively distinguish PB and SP speakers. For example, the
726 model may identify specific pause duration thresholds or spectral tilt values that consistently
727 separate dialect groups. This interpretability makes DT particularly useful for identifying which
728 individual prosodic-acoustic features function as primary dialect markers.

729

730 **4.3.k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN)**

731

732 The k-Nearest Neighbors algorithm classifies speech samples based on their similarity to other
733 samples in the acoustic feature space. Classification is determined by comparing each speech
734 sample to its closest neighbors, using distance metrics such as Euclidean distance. In dialect
735 classification, kNN evaluates how acoustically similar a given participant's speech is to other
736 speakers within each dialect group. If a speaker's acoustic profile—based on features such as f0
737 variability, pause rate, or intensity patterns - closely resembles those of PB speakers, the sample
738 will be classified accordingly. This approach reflects the principle that dialect membership
739 corresponds to clustering in acoustic space, with speakers from the same dialect exhibiting similar
740 prosodic-acoustic profiles.

741 **4.4.Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)**

742

743 Linear Discriminant Analysis is a statistical classification method that identifies linear
744 combinations of acoustic features that maximize separation between dialect groups. It assumes that
745 acoustic variables follow approximately normal distributions and that group variances are
746 comparable. In this study, LDA identifies which combinations of prosodic-acoustic parameters
747 most effectively differentiate PB and SP speakers. For example, it may reveal that a specific
748 combination of pause variability, spectral tilt, and pitch dynamics provides optimal separation
749 between dialects. This method is particularly useful for understanding the relative contribution of
750 multiple acoustic dimensions in defining dialect-specific prosodic features.

751

752 **4.5.Support Vector Machine (SVM)**

753

754 Support Vector Machine is a classification algorithm that identifies the optimal boundary
755 separating dialect groups in the acoustic feature space. It maximizes the distance between the
756 closest observations from each dialect category, thereby improving classification reliability. In
757 dialect classification, SVM evaluates how consistently prosodic-acoustic features distinguish
758 between PB and SP speakers. It is particularly effective when dialect differences are subtle and
759 involve complex interactions between acoustic variables. For instance, if SP speakers
760 systematically exhibit longer pause durations and higher spectral tilt values than PB speakers, SVM
761 identifies the optimal boundary in the acoustic feature space that separates these two groups. When
762 a new speech sample is introduced, the model evaluates its prosodic-acoustic profile relative to this
763 boundary and classifies it as PB or SP depending on which side of the boundary it falls.

764

765 **4.6.Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM)**

766

767 Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) is an ensemble ML technique that builds a sequence of decision
768 trees in a stepwise manner, where each successive tree is trained to correct the classification errors
769 made by the previous ones. Unlike RF, which builds trees independently, GBM constructs trees
770 sequentially, allowing the model to progressively refine its classification performance by focusing
771 on the most difficult cases. In the context of the present research, GBM evaluates how

772 combinations of prosodic-acoustic features contribute incrementally to distinguishing PB and SP
773 speakers. By iteratively prioritizing acoustic observations that are more difficult to classify, the
774 model becomes particularly sensitive to subtle dialect differences reflected in parameters such as
775 pause variability, spectral tilt, and pitch dynamics. This makes GBM especially effective in
776 identifying fine-grained acoustic patterns that may not be captured by simpler models. For
777 example, if most SP speakers are correctly classified based on pause duration alone, but some
778 overlap with PB speakers due to similar pitch variability, GBM will iteratively focus on those
779 ambiguous cases and incorporate additional features - such as spectral tilt - to improve separation.
780 In this way, the model progressively refines classification by correcting previous errors.

781

782 **4.7.Implementation Procedures**

783

784 For the development of the AI-based classifier, a total of 460 speech samples (Table 1, section 2.2)
785 was used. The dataset was randomly partitioned by the dialect classifier into two subsets: 80% of
786 the samples were allocated to training and cross-validation, and the remaining 20% were reserved
787 for testing. In addition, the random selection procedure preserved representation from both dialect
788 groups (PB and SP) across the two subsets. This train–test split is widely adopted in ML research
789 to ensure model generalizability and to prevent overfitting, as it allows the system to learn
790 classification patterns from one portion of the data and evaluate performance on previously unseen
791 samples (James et al., 2013; Brownlee, 2020).

792

793 It is worth highlighting that, in the context of this pilot study, the train–test split was conducted at
794 the sample level rather than at the speaker level. This choice reflects the primary objective of the
795 predictive stage, namely, to assess whether the prosodic-acoustic variables identified as statistically
796 significant in the inferential analysis provide sufficient information to discriminate between PB
797 and SP dialects at the level of individual speech samples. Within this framework, the unit of
798 prediction is the segmented speech sample rather than the unseen speaker. Given that each
799 recording was segmented into multiple speech stretches, yielding a balanced number of
800 observations per dialect, this procedure enables a controlled evaluation of how prosodic-acoustic
801 variation operates across samples under comparable conditions. As such, the present design is
802 consistent with a proof-of-concept approach, in which the focus lies on testing the sensitivity and

803 discriminative capacity of selected acoustic variables within a predictive framework.

804

805 At the same time, it is important to acknowledge that the dataset includes multiple observations
806 derived from the same speakers, which implies that a random split at the sample level may result
807 in observations from a given speaker appearing in both the training and test sets. From a
808 methodological standpoint, this configuration may relax the assumption of independence between
809 subsets and may lead to optimistic estimates of classification performance. As discussed in the
810 literature, random partitioning procedures are appropriate when observations can be treated as
811 independent; however, when related samples are distributed across training and test sets, evaluation
812 metrics may partially reflect shared structure rather than strict generalization (Bishop, 2006; James
813 et al., 2013). In speech processing, this issue is particularly salient, as speaker-dependent and
814 speaker-independent evaluation protocols constitute distinct methodological configurations, with
815 the former typically yielding higher performance due to the presence of speaker-specific
816 information across subsets (Hastie; Tibshirani; Friedman, 2009; Jassim; Abdulmohsin, 2025).
817 Empirical studies in speech classification further demonstrate that evaluation settings which do not
818 control for speaker overlap tend to produce inflated accuracy when compared to speaker-
819 independent setups (Rybka; Janicki, 2013; Atmaja; Sasou, 2022; Sasse et al., 2025).

820

821 Accordingly, the classification results reported in this study should be interpreted as reflecting
822 within-corpus, sample-level performance, rather than a fully speaker-independent estimate of
823 dialect generalization. Importantly, this design remains appropriate for the present stage of
824 research. By aligning predictive modeling with the inferential results obtained through mixed-
825 effects analysis, the current implementation provides an initial validation of the discriminative
826 capacity of prosodic-acoustic features. In this sense, the methodological choice follows the
827 distinction between explanatory and predictive modeling (Shmueli, 2010), in which the present
828 analysis prioritizes feature evaluation and model sensitivity, while recognizing that more restrictive
829 evaluation protocols are required to assess generalization in applied contexts.

830

831 Each classifier was evaluated using Accuracy, computed as the proportion of correctly predicted
832 dialect labels relative to the total number of observations. The complementary Error Rate ($1 -$
833 Accuracy) was also reported to indicate the proportion of misclassified samples. Accuracy is one

834 of the most widely adopted performance metrics in binary classification tasks, particularly when
835 class distributions are balanced (James et al., 2013; Hastie et al., 2009).

836

837 For interpretative purposes, feature-importance values were descriptively categorized according to
838 their empirical distribution within the classifier. Features with scores above 0.30 were treated as
839 dominant, as they represented a substantial proportion of the model’s decision-making process.
840 Values ranging from 0.10 to 0.30 were interpreted as moderately important, indicating predictors
841 that contributed meaningfully to classification but were not independently decisive. Features with
842 values below 0.10 were considered weak contributors, reflecting limited relative influence within
843 the model. It is important to emphasize that these thresholds do not constitute theoretical cutoffs;
844 rather, they serve as analytical conventions adopted to facilitate interpretation of the internal
845 ranking of predictors. As discussed in the literature of model interpretability, feature-importance
846 measures are inherently relative and model-dependent, reflecting each predictor’s contribution
847 within a specific trained model rather than absolute explanatory power (Molnar, 2022).

848

849 **5. Results 2: automatic classification performance**

850

851 Figure 2 presents six confusion matrices illustrating the performance of the AI models used to
852 classify PB and SP speech samples within the dialect classifier. As mentioned in section 4.7, the
853 testing phase corresponded to 20% of the corpus and was randomly partitioned into **92** speech
854 samples ($460_{samples} \times 20\% = 92_{samples}$), comprising **46** PB samples and **46** SP samples.

855

856
857
858
859
860
861

Figure 2: Confusion Matrices for the AI-based binary dialectal classification (PB vs. SP), and the evaluated metrics (Accuracy | Error Rate - ER) based on the *Predictive* values (dialect classification – X-axis), and the *Actual* values (what the samples are in reality – Y-axis). The greener the more correct is the classification.

862
863
864
865

ALT – Figure 2: Six confusion matrices showing the performance of different machine-learning models in classifying PB and SP speech samples. Most cells along with the correct diagonal classification are highlighted in green, indicating high accuracy and few misclassifications across models.

866
867
868
869
870
871
872
873

Results shown in Figure 2 indicate highly consistent discrimination between dialect groups, suggesting that tree-based modeling (GBM, RF and DT) effectively capture the relevant prosodic-acoustic distinctions. It is also important to highlight that identifying a single best classifier is not an objective of this study. Rather, the six models serve as complementary evidence of feature robustness. The convergent performance across all six classifiers, despite their different decision mechanisms, reinforces the conclusion that the identified prosodic-acoustic features provide structurally stable dialect cues rather than algorithm-specific artifacts.

874
875
876
877

Five out of the six ML techniques implemented reached higher than 95% accuracy values in the classification task. The highest classification performance was achieved by the Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM - Figure 2F) with an accuracy of 97.8% (ER = 2.2%) followed by Decision Tree (DT - Figure 2C) and Random Forest (RF – Figure 2D) models, both reaching an accuracy of

878 96.7% (ER = 3.3%). In the sequence, results show *k*-Nearest Neighbors (*k*-NN – Figure 2B) and
879 Support Vector Machine (SVM – Figure 2E) also presenting high accuracy values (95.7%; ER =
880 4.3%). The lowest – but still high - accuracy values came from LDA with a near-95% rate (94.6%;
881 ER = 5.4%). In GBM, 44 out of 46 PB samples and all SP samples were correctly classified. In DT
882 and RF, 44 out of 46 PB samples and 45 out of 46 SP samples were also correctly classified. For
883 *k*-NN and SVM – respectively - 45 out of 46 PB; 43 out of 46 SP samples, and 44 out of 46 PB/SP
884 samples were correctly classified.

885

886 Overall, classification accuracy ranged from 94.6% to 97.8%, with tree models (GBM, RF and DT)
887 consistently yielding the strongest performances. These results indicate that non-linear interactions
888 among prosodic-acoustic features play a substantial role in distinguishing inland PB and SP
889 dialects, reinforcing the robustness of automatic dialect classification in the present dataset based
890 on multiple prosodic-acoustic descriptors.

891

892 Figure 3 presents the relative feature-importance scores derived from the best-performing tree-
893 based models using the Gini impurity reduction criterion. These values reflect the proportional
894 contribution of each prosodic-acoustic parameter to the decision process from the model.

895

896 **Figure 3:** Feature-importance scores based on tree-based models. The prosodic-acoustic features that were
 897 statistically significant on the inferential phase (X-axis, section 3), and Importance scores (Y-axis)
 898 normalized to sum from 0 to 1.

899

900 **ALT – Figure 3:** Bar chart displaying the relative importance of prosodic-acoustic features used in dialect
 901 classification. Pause variability has the highest importance score, followed by intensity-related measures
 902 and other duration features, while pitch-based measures show lower importance.

903

904 The ranking reveals a highly asymmetrical distribution of importance across features. Pause SD
 905 (*pause_sd*) emerges as the dominant predictor, accounting for approximately 0.40 of the total
 906 importance weight. This value alone represents a disproportionately large share of the classifier’s
 907 decision-making process, indicating that variability in pause duration constitutes the most robust
 908 acoustic cue distinguishing between PB and SP speakers in the testing set. This finding directly
 909 aligns with the high overall accuracy observed in the tree models (GBM = 97.8%; RF/DT = 96.7%),
 910 suggesting that much of the classification success is driven by rhythmic-temporal variability rather
 911 than by isolated segmental cues.

912

913 The second most important feature is intensity variation coefficient (*cvint* ~0.22), followed by
914 mean pause duration (*pause_meandur* ~0.14), spectral tilt (*sl_LTAS_alpha* ~0.12), and pause rate
915 (*pause_rate* ~0.08). Together, these parameters reinforce the centrality of rhythmic organization in
916 speech planning (Krivokapić, 2007), and long-term spectral balance (i.e., voice quality) in cross-
917 dialect discrimination. Voice quality in this analysis reflects the degree to which speakers modulate
918 vocal energy across the speech signal. Specifically, the intensity coefficient and spectral tilt capture
919 how PB and SP speakers adjust loudness patterns to signal prominence, emphasis, or expressive
920 variation in speech (Garellek, 2022; Silva Jr.; Barbosa, 2023).

921

922 Notably, the cumulative contribution of pause-related measures exceeds 0.60 of the total
923 importance weight, indicating that rhythmic structuring of speech provides the primary acoustic
924 foundation for dialect separation in the present dataset as suggested by Esling and Edmondson
925 (2011) and Yaeger-Dror and Fagyal (2011). In practical terms, these measures capture how
926 speakers organize silence within the speech stream. The standard deviation of pause duration
927 reflects how consistently or variably speakers distribute pauses; the mean pause duration indicates
928 the typical length of these silent intervals; and pause rate (pauses per second) represents how
929 frequently speakers interrupt speech with pauses. These parameters describe dialect-specific
930 patterns of speech segmentation and pacing, suggesting that PB and SP speakers differ not only in
931 how long they pause but also in how regularly and how often pauses occur throughout the utterance.
932 In contrast, f0-based parameters (*f0sd*, *df0sd_pos*, *f0SAQ* and *df0mean_pos*) exhibit comparatively
933 low importance values (all below 0.03). This distribution suggests that pitch centrality and
934 dynamics alone do not provide sufficiently strong discriminative power to sustain high
935 classification accuracy in this dataset.

936

937 This hierarchy of feature importance helps to explain why tree-based ensemble methods slightly
938 outperformed linear classifiers. Algorithms such as GBM, RF and DT can prioritize dominant
939 predictors (e.g., *pause_sd*) while modeling non-linear interactions among secondary cues, thereby
940 capitalizing on the weighted acoustic structure of the dataset. The classification results therefore
941 do not merely indicate that PB and SP differ acoustically; they reveal how those differences are
942 hierarchically organized within the prosodic system. The heuristic method for using speech feature
943 importance in this pilot study is partially aligned with Zhang (2021), who proposes a hybrid system

944 (traditional ML techniques like the ones used in this study, and Neural Networks) for speech
945 emotion recognition. Zhang's study aimed to obtain the importance of each analyzed acoustic
946 feature for dimensionality reduction (of feature) in speech analysis.

947

948 Therefore, the feature-importance analysis clarifies the internal mechanics of the ASR
949 classification phase: dialect discrimination is primarily structured around rhythmic-temporal
950 pause-based variability, with measures of spectral tilt and vocal effort providing complementary
951 support, and f0-based parameters functioning as less prominent secondary cues. This internal
952 weighting pattern further corroborates the mixed-effects findings discussed earlier, reinforcing the
953 conclusion that dialect differentiation in this research is grounded in rhythmic and intensive
954 organization rather than predominantly in pitch modulation.

955

956 **6. Discussion**

957

958 This study addressed two central research questions concerning the role of prosodic-acoustic
959 features in inland Brazilian Portuguese dialect differentiation and their contribution to automatic
960 dialect classification.

961

962 RQ1 – Do prosodic-acoustic descriptors of duration, f0, intensity, and long-term spectral voice
963 quality provide robust and reliable cues for distinguishing the inland Brazilian Portuguese dialects
964 PB and SP?

965

966 Yes. The present results provide evidence of dialect differentiation. These findings are consistent
967 with earlier prosodic investigations of Brazilian Portuguese dialects. Constantini and Barbosa
968 (2015), for example, analyzed multiple regional varieties using prosodic descriptors derived from
969 vowel-to-vowel rhythmic units and found that several parameters related to duration variability,
970 spectral emphasis, and f0 median significantly differentiated dialect groups. Their results
971 demonstrated that rhythmic parameters, especially variability and asymmetry in duration
972 distributions, play an important role in distinguishing varieties, while intensity-related measures
973 such as spectral emphasis and pitch statistics contribute complementary cues to dialect
974 identification. The authors showed that dialectal contrasts emerged not from a single acoustic

975 dimension but from the interaction of rhythmic, melodic, and intensity-related parameters, a pattern
976 that parallels the hierarchical distribution observed in this work. While the present study's results
977 highlight pause variability and other duration-related measures as dominant predictors in both
978 inferential and machine-learning analyses, the contribution of spectral balance and vocal effort,
979 and pitch parameters remain consistent with the multidimensional prosodic differentiation reported
980 by Constantini and Barbosa (2015). Such results strengthen the sociophonetic interpretation that
981 regional varieties of Brazilian Portuguese are encoded, at least in part, through structured prosodic-
982 acoustic configurations. Since the present study did not include a systematic examination of
983 segmental features, no comparative claim about the relative primacy of prosodic over segmental
984 cues can be drawn from these data alone; the findings demonstrate that prosodic-acoustic
985 dimensions are sufficient to sustain statistically robust dialect differentiation and high-accuracy
986 computational classification within this dataset. These results support the view that rhythmic
987 organization, pitch behavior, and spectral energy distribution are among the dimensions that jointly
988 contribute to dialectal identity, while leaving open the question of how prosodic and segmental
989 dimensions interact in the broader acoustic characterization of these varieties.

990

991 In this respect, the mixed-effects analysis demonstrated that prosodic-acoustic descriptors do
992 indeed provide statistically robust cues for dialect differentiation. By modeling dialect as a fixed
993 effect and speaker as a random effect, the LMEM framework isolated regional variation while
994 controlling for inter-speaker variability (Baayen; Davidson; Bates, 2008; Mirman, 2014). This
995 approach ensures that the observed differences reflect structured dialectal patterning rather than
996 individual performance variability. Across the acoustic domains, duration-related parameters,
997 especially pause variability, displayed the strongest marginal explanatory power. From a
998 sociophonetic perspective, this indicates that rhythmic (pause-based) organization functions as a
999 primary indexical resource distinguishing PB and SP speakers.

1000

1001 Pause variability reflects discourse segmentation, speech planning strategies, and interactional
1002 pacing, dimensions that are socially learned and community specific. Cross-dialect research in
1003 other languages has shown that speech rhythm and temporal structuring frequently serve as salient
1004 regional markers, both for native and foreign dialects (Esling; Edmondson, 2011; Krivokapić,
1005 2007; Silva Jr.; Barbosa, 2019; White; Mattys, 2007). In Brazilian Portuguese, rhythmic patterns

1006 and variation have been documented across several regional varieties (Cagliari; Abaurre, 1986;
1007 Meireles; Gambarini, 2012), but inland dialects have received comparatively limited empirical
1008 attention. The present findings therefore extend Brazilian sociophonetics by demonstrating that
1009 temporal variability is not merely stylistic but structurally embedded in inland dialect
1010 differentiation.

1011

1012 Intensity-related measures, particularly spectral tilt and vocal effort, also significantly contributed
1013 to dialect distinction. Both spectral tilt and vocal effort capture long-term spectral balance and
1014 habitual phonatory settings, indexing voice quality differences between groups (i.e., vocal energy
1015 distribution, prominence, expressive modulation etc.). Voice quality has increasingly been
1016 recognized as a sociophonetic marker capable of signaling regional and social identity (Thomas,
1017 2011; Yaeger-Dror; Fagyal, 2011). The present findings suggest that PB and SP differ not only in
1018 rhythm but also in stable phonation configurations, reinforcing the multidimensional nature of
1019 dialect identity. In contrast, f_0 -based measures, although statistically significant, displayed
1020 comparatively smaller marginal R^2 values, indicating that pitch variability and dynamics function
1021 as secondary but systematic cues. This hierarchy aligns with cross-dialect findings in English and
1022 Spanish, where pitch scaling differences coexist with more dominant rhythmic patterns (Clopper;
1023 Smiljanić, 2011).

1024

1025 It is also worth noting that the presence of zero and near-zero values in the dataset should not be
1026 interpreted solely as artifacts, but rather as an intrinsic characteristic of acoustic-prosodic
1027 representation. Within standard feature extraction frameworks such as GeMAPS (Eyben et al.,
1028 2016), zero values are used to encode unvoiced regions (e.g., $f_0 = 0$), thereby capturing the absence
1029 of phonatory activity. In this sense, zero values contribute directly to the modeling of rhythmic
1030 and, more modestly, melodic structures, particularly in pause-related measures. This is consistent
1031 with the present findings, in which duration-based parameters emerged as the strongest predictors
1032 of dialectal variation between PB and SP dialects. In relation to the extreme values observed in the
1033 dataset, they were retained because acoustic-prosodic measures are inherently sensitive to both
1034 linguistic variability and signal-dependent factors. In speech analysis, domains such as duration,
1035 intensity, and f_0 may naturally exhibit wide ranges due to differences in speech rate, pausing
1036 behavior, and intensity emphasis. Values consistent with natural speech production, such as

1037 extended pauses or abrupt pitch movements, were retained as they contribute to the representation
1038 of prosodic structure.

1039

1040 RQ2. To what extent can automatic dialect classification be explained by the relative contribution
1041 of prosodic-acoustic features, and how do these features affect ASR performance?

1042

1043 The automatic classification results further clarify how these acoustic dimensions operate in
1044 applied computational systems. The high classification accuracy rates observed in the predictive
1045 phase (ranging from 94.6% to 97.8%) demonstrate that the dialectal patterns identified through
1046 statistical modeling are sufficiently structured to allow reliable prediction of dialect membership
1047 in previously unseen speech samples. Importantly, the feature-importance ranking derived from
1048 the Gini impurity reduction method mirrors the inferential results obtained in the mixed-effects
1049 analysis. Pause variability emerged as the dominant predictor (~0.43 importance weight), followed
1050 by additional duration and intensity-related measures, whereas f0-based parameters occupied
1051 comparatively lower positions in the hierarchy of predictive relevance. This convergence between
1052 inferential effect sizes and predictive feature importance strengthens the construct validity of the
1053 prosodic-acoustic parameters identified as dialect markers and confirms their explanatory and
1054 predictive relevance for dialect classification tasks (Bishop, 2006; Emara; Shaker, 2024; Molnar,
1055 2022). As discussed previously, this alignment reflects the complementary goals of explanatory
1056 and predictive modeling frameworks (Shmueli, 2010; Yarkoni; Westfall, 2017). The inferential
1057 phase established which acoustic dimensions significantly account for cross-dialect variance while
1058 controlling for inter-speaker variability, whereas the predictive phase evaluated whether these same
1059 dimensions generalize effectively in classification tasks.

1060

1061 The fact that duration-related parameters both explain dialect variance and dominate feature-
1062 importance rankings suggests that rhythmic structuring constitutes the primary acoustic dimension
1063 influencing ASR performance in the present dataset, and for these two inland Brazilian Portuguese
1064 varieties specifically. The primacy of rhythmic parameters observed here reflects the prosodic
1065 organization of PB and SP as documented in this corpus; it should not be assumed that the same
1066 hierarchy applies to other dialectal contrasts or other languages. Cross-linguistic research has
1067 consistently shown that the relative contribution of f0, duration, and intensity to dialect and accent

1068 differentiation varies considerably depending on the specific varieties under comparison, the
1069 phonological systems involved, and the acoustic dimensions that carry social meaning in each
1070 community (Thomas, 2011; White; Mattys, 2007). Whether durational parameters maintain their
1071 dominant role in other Brazilian Portuguese regional contrasts, or whether f0 or voice quality
1072 dimensions assume greater prominence in other variety pairs, remains an open empirical question
1073 that future research must address.

1074

1075 From an applied perspective, this finding indicates that systems trained on Brazilian Portuguese
1076 must account for dialect-specific (or dialect-grouped) rhythmic organization to achieve consistent
1077 recognition performance. In this sense, the observed temporal parameters may function as potential
1078 sociophonetic markers of dialect differentiation, reflecting systematic differences in rhythmic
1079 organization between PB and SP speakers. However, given the pilot nature of this research, and
1080 based on a limited dataset, these acoustic patterns should be interpreted cautiously and require
1081 validation through larger and more heterogeneous corpora. Future research should examine
1082 whether such cues remain stable across multiple dimensions of intra-dialect variation: across age
1083 groups, sex and gender, socioeconomic strata, rural-urban continua, and different speech registers
1084 or task types within the same regional variety. The present pilot does not permit such distinctions,
1085 given that all participants were young university students from comparable academic and
1086 institutional contexts. Establishing the stability of these prosodic markers across sociolinguistic
1087 stratification is a necessary step toward validating their status as robust dialect-level features rather
1088 than community- or context-specific patterns.

1089

1090 Sociophonetic research has demonstrated that dialectal identity emerges from gradient distributions
1091 of phonetic features that may vary according to social and geographic factors rather than from
1092 single categorical markers (Thomas, 2011; Yaeger-Dror; Fagyal, 2011). Consequently, while the
1093 present results suggest that rhythmic parameters may serve as reliable indicators of PB–SP
1094 differentiation, further investigation is necessary to determine the extent to which these patterns
1095 generalize across speakers and sociolinguistic contexts. Such observations are consistent with
1096 previous research demonstrating that automatic dialect classification is particularly sensitive to
1097 sociophonetic variability in speech production (Jassim; Abdulmohsin, 2025; Wassink; Gansen;
1098 Bartholomew, 2022).

1099 The present results are also consistent with previous work on automatic classification of Brazilian
1100 regional accents, which has shown that acoustic modeling techniques can successfully capture
1101 structured dialectal variation in speech signals. In a comprehensive investigation of accent
1102 classification in Brazilian Portuguese, Batista (2019) demonstrated that statistical and machine
1103 learning approaches can achieve reliable classification of regional speech varieties by modeling
1104 acoustic representations extracted from speech corpora. Her work also highlights that classification
1105 performance may vary depending on the evaluation scenario, with cross-dataset testing presenting
1106 greater challenges due to differences in recording conditions and speaker populations. This
1107 observation aligns with the current results suggesting that dialect-sensitive acoustic patterns must
1108 be sufficiently stable to generalize across speakers and recording contexts. In this sense, the high
1109 classification accuracy observed further supports the argument that regional dialect differences are
1110 encoded in systematic prosodic-acoustic configurations that can be detected not only through
1111 inferential statistical modeling but also through predictive computational systems.

1112

1113 In broader terms, the integration of mixed-effects modeling and machine learning classification
1114 strengthens the theoretical interpretation of dialect differentiation (Hay, 2011). As noted in
1115 sociophonetic research, combining inferential statistical approaches with computational
1116 classification techniques provides a particularly productive methodological toolkit for analyzing
1117 structured phonetic variation. Mixed-effects models allow researchers to estimate the influence of
1118 linguistic predictors while accounting for speaker-level variability, whereas tree-based and other
1119 ML methods can detect complex interactions among acoustic features that may characterize
1120 dialectal patterns. In line with broader methodological discussions distinguishing explanatory and
1121 predictive modeling in quantitative research (Hay, 2011; Shmueli, 2010; Yarkoni; Westfall, 2017),
1122 this work integrates both approaches through two complementary analytical phases: an inferential
1123 stage based on corpus design, acoustic extraction procedures, and mixed-effects statistical analysis
1124 (Methodology 1, section 2), and a predictive stage based on automatic dialect classification using
1125 ML techniques (Methodology 2, section 4). This dual framework identifies statistically significant
1126 acoustic variables of dialect variation and evaluates their discriminative power in classification
1127 tasks.

1128

1129 Moreover, rather than treating dialect categories as discrete phonological entities, the present

1130 findings support a gradient, usage-based perspective in which dialect identity emerges from
1131 weighted distributions of prosodic-acoustic features. Within this hierarchy, rhythmic organization
1132 appears as the dominant dimension of sociophonetic differentiation, followed by spectral–intensity
1133 patterns and more subtle pitch-related variability.

1134

1135 Although the present study focuses on automatic dialect classification rather than speech synthesis,
1136 the findings can be interpreted in light of recent work on prosody modeling in speech technologies.
1137 As mentioned in section 1, Galdino et al. (2025) conducted a systematic review of prosody
1138 evaluation in speech synthesis systems showing that most computational approaches rely primarily
1139 on f0-based descriptors, followed by duration and intensity, reflecting a strong emphasis on pitch-
1140 related modeling in current speech technologies. In contrast, the results obtained in this research
1141 suggest a different hierarchical organization for the dialectal differentiation investigated here, in
1142 which durational-rhythmic parameters, particularly pause-based measures, emerge as the most
1143 informative predictors, followed by intensity-related measures and more secondary contributions
1144 from f0. This contrast highlights the importance of investigating prosodic-acoustic structure in
1145 specific linguistic and dialectal contexts. In particular, the literature on speech synthesis also
1146 emphasizes that many languages and dialects remain underrepresented in prosody modeling,
1147 largely due to data scarcity and limited annotated speech corpora. The present results therefore
1148 contribute to addressing this gap by providing empirical evidence on how prosodic-acoustic cues
1149 operate in two inland varieties of Brazilian Portuguese, offering insights that may inform both
1150 dialect-aware speech technologies and sociophonetic descriptions of regional speech variation
1151 (Mehralian; Van Hamme, 2025).

1152

1153 It is essential to note that a limitation of the present classification concerns the use of a sample-
1154 level train–test split, which may allow observations derived from the same speaker to be included
1155 in both the training and test sets. Because the dataset consists of multiple segmented samples per
1156 speaker, this design introduces a degree of dependency between subsets and therefore relaxes the
1157 assumption of independence underlying standard evaluation procedures. Consequently, the
1158 reported classification accuracy should be interpreted with caution, as it may represent an upper-
1159 bound estimate of performance when compared to a strictly speaker-independent evaluation.
1160 Methodological research has consistently shown that when related observations are shared across

1161 partitions, performance metrics may be inflated due to partial overlap in speaker-specific
1162 characteristics (Bishop, 2006; James et al., 2013). In speech-related tasks, this distinction is
1163 particularly well established, with speaker-dependent configurations consistently outperforming
1164 speaker-independent ones because they do not fully control for inter-speaker variability (Hastie;
1165 Tibshirani; Friedman, 2009; Jassim; Abdulmohsin, 2025). Empirical evidence from speech
1166 classification studies reinforces this point by demonstrating that evaluation procedures allowing
1167 speaker overlap between training and test sets can yield substantially higher accuracy than those
1168 enforcing speaker independence (Rybka; Janicki, 2013; Atmaja; Sasou, 2022; Sasse et al., 2025).

1169

1170 Despite this limitation, the present findings remain informative within the scope of a pilot
1171 investigation. The use of a sample-level split was motivated by the need to evaluate whether the
1172 prosodic-acoustic variables identified as statistically significant in the inferential stage, especially
1173 those related to rhythmic organization, are sufficiently robust to support dialect classification in a
1174 predictive setting. The observed convergence between mixed-effects modeling and feature-
1175 importance rankings provides consistent evidence that these variables encode structured dialectal
1176 differences. However, the interpretation of classification performance must remain
1177 methodologically cautious, as the current design prioritizes feature sensitivity over strict
1178 generalization.

1179

1180 The results addressing RQ1 and RQ2 support the hypotheses proposed in this study. The analyses
1181 demonstrate that prosodic-acoustic descriptors derived from duration, intensity, and f_0 provide
1182 statistically consistent cues for distinguishing the inland Brazilian Portuguese dialects PB and SP.
1183 Feature-importance analyses revealed a hierarchical contribution of acoustic parameters, with
1184 pause-based rhythmic variability emerging as the dominant dimension in dialect classification. The
1185 convergence between inferential statistical modeling and predictive machine-learning results
1186 indicates that dialect differentiation in inland Brazilian Portuguese is not only statistically
1187 observable but also computationally detectable.

1188

1189 These findings therefore confirm the initial hypothesis that prosodic-acoustic features provide
1190 reliable cues for automatic dialect classification and that their relative contribution follows a
1191 structured hierarchy across acoustic domains. In broader terms, by providing converging

1192 explanatory and predictive evidence, this study reinforces the technological relevance of dialect-
1193 sensitive acoustic modeling for ASR systems while also highlighting the sociophonetic importance
1194 of documenting and analyzing minoritized and under-researched inland dialects, which remain
1195 underrepresented in the development of intelligent speech technologies.

1196

1197 **7. Conclusion**

1198

1199 This study makes two complementary contributions: a sociophonetic characterization of the
1200 prosodic-acoustic structure distinguishing two inland Brazilian Portuguese varieties (PB-SP), and
1201 a computational validation of that structure through automatic dialect classification. By integrating
1202 inferential statistical mixed-effects modeling with predictive machine-learning classification, the
1203 study demonstrated that dialect differentiation between PB and SP is acoustically structured,
1204 hierarchically organized, and computationally detectable. It is worth emphasizing that neither stage
1205 is subordinate to the other; together, they constitute a dual inferential–predictive framework in
1206 which statistical evidence and machine-learning performance point in the same analytical direction,
1207 mutually reinforcing the overall interpretation of the findings.

1208

1209 The results demonstrate that rhythmic organization, particularly pause variability, emerges as the
1210 primary acoustic dimension distinguishing the two inland dialects, within this dataset and for these
1211 two Brazilian Portuguese varieties specifically. This hierarchical ordering should not be
1212 generalized to other language varieties or dialectal contrasts without independent empirical
1213 validation, as the relative weighting of prosodic dimensions in dialect differentiation is known to
1214 vary across linguistic systems and sociolinguistic contexts. Spectral tilt and intensity-related
1215 measures contribute meaningfully, suggesting that habitual phonatory settings, voice quality, and
1216 vocal effort also encode dialect identity. Although f_0 -based parameters show statistically
1217 significant differences, they function as secondary cues within the overall hierarchy of prosodic
1218 weighting. The convergence between mixed-effects results and feature-importance rankings
1219 reinforces the construct validity of these acoustic parameters and confirms that the same features
1220 explaining dialect variance also sustain high predictive performance in ASR classification.

1221

1222 From a sociophonetic standpoint, the results underscore that inland dialect identity in Brazilian

1223 Portuguese is encoded not merely in segmental differences but also in structured prosodic
1224 configurations. The dominance of temporal organization suggests that rhythm operates as a socially
1225 embedded indexical resource, contributing to regional differentiation. By focusing on inland
1226 varieties that remain comparatively underrepresented in speech research and technology
1227 development, this study expands the empirical coverage of Brazilian Portuguese dialectology and
1228 highlights the importance of incorporating minority and under-researched dialects into
1229 computational modeling.

1230

1231 Technologically, the findings demonstrate that dialect-aware systems benefit from integrating
1232 rhythm-sensitive acoustic features (Mehralian; Van Hamme, 2025). The high classification
1233 accuracy achieved across models confirms that prosodic-acoustic variation is stable enough to
1234 support reliable dialect discrimination. This dual inferential–predictive validation strengthens both
1235 the sociophonetic interpretation of the results and their practical implications for intelligent speech
1236 technology.

1237

1238 **8. Limitations and Future Directions**

1239

1240 Despite the robustness of these initial findings, several limitations must be acknowledged. First,
1241 the sample size was relatively modest — 20 speakers yielding approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes
1242 of recorded audio used to train the classifiers, and although the use of mixed-effects modeling
1243 accounts for speaker-level variability, broader sampling across age groups, educational
1244 backgrounds, and sociolinguistic profiles would enhance generalizability. Future studies should
1245 incorporate larger and more socially diverse speaker groups to further test the stability of the
1246 identified acoustic hierarchies.

1247

1248 Second, the corpus consisted of reading speech derived from a podcast script. While this ensured
1249 phonetic control and comparability across speakers, it may not fully capture spontaneous prosodic
1250 variation. Given that rhythm and pause organization are sensitive to discourse context, future
1251 research should examine whether similar hierarchical patterns emerge in semi-spontaneous or
1252 conversational speech.

1253

1254 Third, the classification phase relied on a predefined set of prosodic-acoustic features. Although
1255 the feature-importance ranking revealed a clear hierarchy, additional acoustic dimensions, such as
1256 segmental features, spectral moments, dynamic intonational contours, voice quality features, or
1257 duration-based descriptors could further refine dialect discrimination. Furthermore, incorporating
1258 articulatory measures, as suggested in recent dialect research (e.g., Wieling; Tiede; Tomaschek,
1259 2017), may provide complementary insights into regional variation.

1260

1261 Fourth, while this work focused on binary dialect classification (PB vs. SP), Brazilian Portuguese
1262 exhibits a rich continuum of regional varieties. Expanding the framework to multi-dialect
1263 classification tasks would allow testing whether the hierarchical dominance of rhythmic
1264 organization observed here generalizes across broader dialectal comparisons. Such an expansion
1265 would also help identify and validate sociophonetic markers that can differentiate regional speech
1266 patterns, providing a clearer understanding of how dialect identity is encoded in prosodic-acoustic
1267 structures. Beyond theoretical implications, incorporating these markers into computational models
1268 could significantly improve dialect-aware systems operating in linguistically diverse environments
1269 (Mehralian; Van Hamme, 2025).

1270

1271 Finally, future research should extend the present framework by implementing speaker-level
1272 partitioning strategies for the train-test split, in which all samples from a given speaker are assigned
1273 exclusively to either the training or test set. Such an approach would provide a more conservative
1274 and ecologically valid evaluation of how well the identified prosodic-acoustic features generalize
1275 to unseen speakers, which is essential for real-world ASR applications. In addition, expanding the
1276 dataset to include a larger and more diverse pool of speakers, including intra-dialectal variation
1277 (e.g., rural and urban accents), would further strengthen the robustness of classification models.
1278 Within this perspective, the present study should be understood as an initial step that establishes
1279 the acoustic and hierarchical structure of dialect differentiation, while also delineating the
1280 methodological pathway for subsequent, more stringent evaluations.

1281

1282 If future research addresses the limitations outlined above, particularly through larger and more
1283 socially diverse samples, spontaneous speech data, and expanded dialect comparisons, the findings
1284 may offer significant potential for both forensic and pedagogical applications. In forensic scenarios,

1285 the identification of hierarchically weighted prosodic-acoustic (or segmental) markers, such as
1286 pause variability and spectral measures of voice quality, may contribute to more reliable speaker
1287 profiling and regional attribution in cases involving dialect-sensitive analysis. From a pedagogical
1288 perspective, understanding which prosodic dimensions systematically differentiate inland Brazilian
1289 Portuguese dialects can promote greater awareness of linguistic diversity in educational contexts,
1290 reducing stigmatization of non-metropolitan varieties and supporting accent-inclusive language
1291 teaching practices.

1292

1293 **Competing interests**

1294 The authors declare no competing interests.

1295

1296 **Preprint**

1297 The research manuscript is openly available in **Zenodo** at:
1298 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20549075>.

1299

1300 **Data Availability Statement**

1301 The data, code, and materials that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo
1302 at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19421930>. The repository contains the following components:
1303 (i) two datasets used for both the inferential and predictive analyses; (ii) Praat scripts for the
1304 complete acoustic processing pipeline, including inferential and predictive procedures; (iii) an R
1305 function script for running the Linear Mixed-Effects Models used in the inferential analysis; and
1306 (iv) Python scripts for running each machine-learning algorithm presented in this study. For items
1307 (ii), (iii), and (iv), usage instructions are provided in two formats: (a) a detailed step-by-step, line-
1308 by-line User Manual; and (b) a README.md file accompanying each script.

1309

1310 The raw audio recordings cannot be shared publicly due to participant confidentiality requirements
1311 established by the ethics committee approval (CAAE 67001923.9.1001.8142). Access to restricted
1312 data may be requested by contacting Luciani Ester Tenani (UNESP) at luciani.tenani@unesp.br,
1313 subject to the approval of the requesting researcher's institutional ethics committee and the signing
1314 of a data access agreement. These files are part of the BrAMCorp database (UNICAMP –
1315 FAPESP), which is currently under development and expected to become publicly available in

1316 2027.

1317

1318 **Funding Sources**

1319 This research received financial support from the National Council for Scientific and Technological
1320 Development (CNPq), Brazil. Leônidas Silva Jr. was supported by CNPq under grant
1321 [307010/2022-8], and Luciani E. Tenani was supported by CNPq under grant [304567/2024-8] and
1322 by FAPESP under grant [2022/05908-0].

1323

1324 **AI Use Statement**

1325 The authors declare that no artificial intelligence (AI) tools were used at any stage of this research,
1326 including data collection, analysis, interpretation, or manuscript preparation.

1327

1328 **Ethics Statement**

1329 This study was conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines for research involving human
1330 participants. The audio recordings analyzed were collected as part of the research project
1331 *"University learners in contemporary academic-scientific literacy practices in the training of*
1332 *elementary education teachers and globalized researchers"* (FAPESP Grant no. 2022/05908-0),
1333 which was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the State University of Campinas
1334 (CEP/UNICAMP) under approval number CAAE 67001923.9.1001.8142.

1335

1336 All participants provided informed consent prior to participation. The consent procedure was
1337 administered by the second author, a researcher formally affiliated with the approved project.
1338 Participants authorized the recording and use of their speech data for scientific research purposes.
1339 For the purposes of this study, all speech samples were anonymized prior to analysis: speaker
1340 identities were replaced by codes, and no personally identifiable information is reported or
1341 disclosed in this manuscript or in the associated open materials deposited in Zenodo
1342 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19421930>).

1343

1344 The raw audio recordings cannot be shared publicly due to participant confidentiality requirements
1345 established by the ethics committee approval (CAAE 67001923.9.1001.8142). Access to restricted
1346 data may be requested by contacting Luciani Ester Tenani (UNESP) at luciani.tenani@unesp.br,

1347 subject to the approval of the requesting researcher’s institutional ethics committee and the signing
1348 of a data access agreement. These files are part of the BrAMCorp database (UNICAMP –
1349 FAPESP), which is currently under development and expected to become publicly available in
1350 2027.

1351

1352 The database as a whole has not yet completed the full anonymization procedures required for
1353 unrestricted public release. For this reason, the raw audio files remain restricted at this stage and
1354 are accessible only to members of the FAPESP research team responsible for data collection, in
1355 accordance with the ethical terms of the approved project. Public access is expected to become
1356 available in 2027 via the *Letramento Contemporâneo* platform, once the required anonymization
1357 and platform development processes are complete. The second author, as a member of that research
1358 team, authorized the use of the relevant materials in this study under the conditions established in
1359 the approved project, ensuring full compliance with the approved ethical guidelines and the non-
1360 disclosure of participants' identifiable data. For further details on access conditions, see the Data
1361 Availability Statement.

1362

1363 **References**

1364 AKIS, E.; BELL, S.; SIMPSON, D. Objective measures of auditory temporal resolution with
1365 ABR. *International Journal of Audiology*, v. 64, n. 11, p. 1095-1105, 2025. DOI:
1366 <https://doi.org/10.1080/14992027.2025.2486847>.

1367 ATMAJA, B. T.; SASOU, A. Effect of different splitting criteria on the performance of speech
1368 emotion recognition. In: *IEEE REGION 10 CONFERENCE (IEEE TENCON 2022)*, p. 760–764,
1369 2022.

1370 BAAYEN, R. H.; DAVIDSON, D. J.; BATES, D. M. Mixed-effects modeling with crossed
1371 random effects for subjects and items. *Journal of Memory and Language*, v. 59, n. 4, p. 390–412,
1372 2008. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2007.12.005>.

1373 BARBOSA, P. *Incursões em torno do ritmo da fala*. Campinas: Pontes, 2006.

1374 BARBOSA, P.; ALVARENGA, L. The interplay between syllabic duration and melody to signal
1375 prosodic functions in reading and story retelling in Brazilian Portuguese. *Languages*, v. 9, n. 268,
1376 p. 1-18, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages9080268>.

1377 BARBOSA, P.; MADUREIRA, S. *Manual de fonética acústica experimental: aplicações a*
1378 *dados do português brasileiro*. São Paulo: Cortez, 2015.

1379 BARR, D. J.; LEVY, R.; SCHEEPERS, C.; TILY, H. J. Random effects structure for
1380 confirmatory hypothesis testing: Keep it maximal. *Journal of Memory and Language*, v. 68, n. 3,
1381 p. 255–278, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2012.11.001>.

- 1382 BATISTA, N. *Estudo sobre identificação automática de sotaques regionais brasileiros baseada*
1383 *em modelagens estatísticas e técnicas de aprendizado de máquina*. 2019. Dissertação (Mestrado
1384 em Engenharia Elétrica – Telecomunicações e Telemática) – Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica e
1385 de Computação, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas, 2019.
- 1386 BEHRAVAN, H. *Advances in automatic foreign accent recognition*. 2016. PhD Dissertation –
1387 University of Eastern Finland, Joensuu, 2016.
- 1388 BISHOP, C. M. *Pattern recognition and machine learning*. New York: Springer, 2006.
- 1389 BOERSMA, P.; WEENINK, D. *Praat: doing phonetics by computer*. Version 6.1.38. Computer
1390 software. Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam, 2024. Available at: <https://www.praat.org/>.
- 1391 BRAID, A. *Fonética forense*. 2. ed. Campinas: Millennium, 2003.
- 1392 BROWNLEE, J. *Train-test split for evaluating machine learning algorithms*. Python Machine
1393 Learning, v. 79, p. 1–12, 2020.
- 1394 CAGLIARI, L.; ABAURRE, M. Elementos para uma investigação instrumental das relações
1395 entre padrões rítmicos e processos fonológicos no português brasileiro. *Caderno de Estudos*
1396 *Linguísticos*, v. 10, p. 39-57, 1986.
- 1397 CANTONI, M. M.; OLIVEIRA, B. G.; NEVADO, H. M. Introdução à análise acústica da fala
1398 com o Praat. *Texto Livre: Linguagem e Tecnologia*, v. 15, p. e37947, 2022. DOI:
1399 <https://doi.org/10.35699/1983-3652.2022.37947>.
- 1400 CHAN, M. P. Y.; CHOE, J.; LI, A.; CHEN, Y.; GAO, X.; HOLLIDAY, N. Training and
1401 typological bias in ASR performance for world Englishes. In: INTERSPEECH 2022, 2022,
1402 Incheon. *Proceedings of Interspeech 2022*. [S.l.]: International Speech Communication
1403 Association, 2022. p. 1273–1277. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2022-10869>.
- 1404 CHIN, W. W. Issues and opinion on structural equation modeling. *MIS Quarterly*, v. 22, n. 1, p.
1405 vii–xvi, 1998. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/249674>.
- 1406 CLOPPER, C. G.; SMILJANIĆ, R. Effects of gender and regional dialect on prosodic patterns in
1407 American English. *Journal of Phonetics*, v. 39, n. 2, p. 237–245, 2011. DOI:
1408 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2011.02.006>.
- 1409 COHEN, J. A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*, v. 112, n. 1, p. 155–159, 1992. DOI:
1410 <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.112.1.155>.
- 1411 CONSTANTINI, A.; BARBOSA, P. Prosodic characteristics of different varieties of Brazilian
1412 Portuguese. *Revista Brasileira de Criminalística*, v. 4, n. 3, p. 44–53, 2015. DOI:
1413 10.15260/rbc.v4i3.103.
- 1414 CRAVEIRO, G.; SANTOS, V.; DALALANA, G.; SVARTMAN, F.; ALUÍSIO, S. Simple and
1415 fast automatic prosodic segmentation of Brazilian Portuguese spontaneous speech. In:
1416 *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Processing of Portuguese* –
1417 v. 1. Association for Computational Linguistics, p. 32–44, 2024.
- 1418 EMARA, I. F.; SHAKER, N. H. The impact of non-native English speakers’ phonological and
1419 prosodic features on automatic speech recognition accuracy. *Speech Communication*, v. 157,
1420 Article 103038, p. 1–12, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.specom.2024.103038>.
- 1421 ESLING, J.; EDMONDSON, J. Acoustical analysis of voice quality for sociophonetic purposes.

- 1422 In: DI PAOLO, M.; YAEGER-DROR, M. (eds.). *Sociophonetics: a student's guide*. London:
1423 Routledge, p. 131–148, 2011.
- 1424 EYBEN, F.; SCHERER, K.; SCHULLER, B.; SUNDBERG, J.; ANDRÉ, E.; BUSSO, C.;
1425 DEVILLERS, L.; EPPS, J.; LAUKKA, P.; NARAYANAN, S.; TRUONG, K. The Geneva
1426 Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set (GeMAPS) for voice research and affective computing.
1427 *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, v. 7, n. 2, p. 190–202, 2016. DOI:
1428 <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAFFC.2015.2457417>.
- 1429 FLEGE, J. Second language speech learning: theory, findings and problems. In: STRANGE, W.
1430 (ed.). *Speech perception and linguistic experience: issues in cross-language research*. Timonium,
1431 MD: York Press, 1995. p. 233–277.
- 1432 GARELLEK, M. Theoretical achievements of phonetics in the 21st century: Phonetics of voice
1433 quality. *Journal of Phonetics*, v. 94, p. 1-22, 2022. DOI:
1434 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2022.101155>.
- 1435 GALDINO, J.; MATOS, A.; SVARTMAN, F.; ALUISIO, S. The evaluation of prosody in
1436 speech synthesis: a systematic review. *Journal of the Brazilian Computer Society*, v. 31, n. 1,
1437 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5753/jbcs.2025.5468>.
- 1438 GAUY, M.; FINGER, M. Acoustic models of Brazilian Portuguese speech based on neural
1439 transformers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2312.09265*, 2023. DOI:
1440 <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.09265>.
- 1441 HASTIE, T.; TIBSHIRANI, R.; FRIEDMAN, J. *The elements of statistical learning: data
1442 mining, inference, and prediction*. 2. ed. New York: Springer, 2009.
- 1443 HAY, J. Statistical analysis. In: DI PAOLO, M.; YAEGER-DROR, M. (eds.). *Sociophonetics: a
1444 student's guide*. London: Routledge, p. 198–214, 2011.
- 1445 HENSELER, J.; RINGLE, C.; SINKOVICS, R. The use of partial least squares path modeling in
1446 international marketing. In: SINKOVICS, R.; GHOURI, P. (eds.). *New challenges to
1447 international marketing*. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing, 2009. p. 277–320. DOI:
1448 [https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979\(2009\)0000020014](https://doi.org/10.1108/S1474-7979(2009)0000020014).
- 1449 HIRST, D. The analysis by synthesis of speech melody: from data to models. *Journal of Speech
1450 Sciences*, v. 1, n. 1, p. 55-83, 2011. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20396/joss.v1i1.15011>.
- 1451 JAMES, G.; WITTEN, D.; HASTIE, T.; TIBSHIRANI, R. *An introduction to statistical
1452 learning: with applications in R*. New York: Springer, 2013.
- 1453 JASSIM, S.; ABDULMOHSIN, H. Accent Classification Using Machine Learning Techniques:
1454 A Review. *International Journal of Computer Information Systems and Industrial Management
1455 Applications*, v. 17, p. 421–451, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.70917/ijcisim-2025-0028>.
- 1456 KISLER, T.; REICHEL, U. D.; SCHIEL, F. *Multilingual processing of speech via web services*.
1457 *Computer Speech & Language*, v. 45, p. 326–347, 2017. DOI:
1458 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csl.2016.11.005>. Available at: [https://clarin.phonetik.uni-
1459 muenchen.de/BASWebServices/interface/WebMAUSBasic](https://clarin.phonetik.uni-muenchen.de/BASWebServices/interface/WebMAUSBasic).
- 1460 KOENECKE, A.; NAM, A.; LAKE, E.; NUDELL, J.; QUARTEY, M.; MENGESHA, Z.;
1461 TOUPS, C.; RICKFORD, J. R.; JURAFSKY, D.; GOEL, S. Racial disparities in automated
1462 speech recognition. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, v. 117, n. 14, p. 7684–

- 1463 7689, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1915768117>.
- 1464 KRIVOKAPIĆ, J. Prosodic planning: Effects of phrasal length and complexity on pause duration.
1465 *Journal of Phonetics*, v. 35, n. 2, p. 162-179, 2007. DOI:
1466 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2006.04.001>.
- 1467 KUMAR, Y.; SINGH, N. A comprehensive view of automatic speech recognition system – a
1468 systematic literature review. In: 2019 International Conference on Automation, Computational
1469 and Technology Management (ICACTM). IEEE, 2019. p. 168–173. DOI:
1470 <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACTM.2019.8776714>.
- 1471 LADEFOGED, P. *Phonetic data analysis: an introduction to fieldwork and instrumental*
1472 *techniques*. Malden: Blackwell, 2003.
- 1473 MARKL, N. Language variation and algorithmic bias: understanding algorithmic bias in British
1474 English automatic speech recognition. In: ACM CONFERENCE ON FAIRNESS,
1475 ACCOUNTABILITY, AND TRANSPARENCY (FAccT 2022), 5., 2022, Seoul. *Proceedings of*
1476 *the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*. New York:
1477 Association for Computing Machinery, 2022. p. 521–534. DOI:
1478 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533117>.
- 1479 MEHRALIAN, P.; VAN HAMME, H. Leveraging geographic metadata for dialect-aware speech
1480 recognition. In: *Proceedings of International Speech Communication Association*
1481 *(INTERSPEECH 2025)*, p. 1153–1157, 2025. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2025-](https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2025-1839)
1482 [1839](https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2025-1839).
- 1483 MEIRELES, A.; GAMBARINI, V. Rhythm typology of Brazilian Portuguese dialects. In: 6th
1484 International Conference on Speech Prosody, 6., 2012. *Proceedings of Speech Prosody 2012*, p.
1485 474-477, 2012.
- 1486 MIRMAN, D. *Growth curve analysis and visualization using R*. Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2014.
- 1487 MOKSONY, F. Small is beautiful: the use and interpretation of R^2 in social research.
1488 *Szociológiai Szemle*, p. 130–138, 1999.
- 1489 MOLNAR, C. *Interpretable machine learning*. 2. ed. [S.l.]: Lulu.com, 2022. Available at:
1490 <https://christophm.github.io/interpretable-ml-book/>.
- 1491 MOYER, A. *Foreign accent: the phenomenon of non-native speech*. Cambridge: Cambridge
1492 University Press, 2013.
- 1493 NAKAGAWA, S.; SCHIELZETH, H. A general and simple method for obtaining R^2 from
1494 generalized linear mixed-effects models. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, v. 4, n. 2, p. 133–
1495 142, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210x.2012.00261.x>.
- 1496 NIELSEN, A. *Análise prática de séries temporais: predição com estatística e aprendizado de*
1497 *máquina*. Tradução de Cibelle Ravaglia. Rio de Janeiro: Alta Books, 2021.
- 1498 ORTEGA-LLEBARIA, M.; SILVA JR., L.; NAGAO, J. Macro and micro-rhythm in L2 English:
1499 exploration and refinement of measures. In: SKARNITZL, R.; VOLÍN, J. (eds.). *Proceedings of*
1500 *the 20th International Congress of Phonetic Sciences*, 2023. p. 1582–1586. Available at:
1501 [https://www.internationalphoneticassociation.org/icphs-](https://www.internationalphoneticassociation.org/icphs-proceedings/ICPhS2023/full_papers/830.pdf)
1502 [proceedings/ICPhS2023/full_papers/830.pdf](https://www.internationalphoneticassociation.org/icphs-proceedings/ICPhS2023/full_papers/830.pdf).
- 1503 R CORE TEAM. R: *A language and environment for statistical computing*. Computer software.

- 1504 Vienna: R Foundation for Statistical Computing, 2026. Available at: <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- 1505 RYBKA, J.; JANICKI, A. Comparison of speaker dependent and speaker independent emotion
1506 recognition. *International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science*, v. 23, n. 4, p.
1507 797–808, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2478/amcs-2013-0060>.
- 1508 SASSE, L.; NICOLAISEN-SOBESKY, E.; DUKART, J.; EICKHOFF, S. B.; GÖTZ, M.;
1509 HAMDAN, S.; KOMAYER, V.; KULKARNI, A.; LAHNAKOSKI, J. M.; LOVE, B. C.;
1510 RAIMONDO, F.; PATIL, K. R. Overview of leakage scenarios in supervised machine learning.
1511 *Journal of Big Data*, v. 12, n. 1, p. 135, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-025-01193-8>.
- 1512 SHMUELI, G. To explain or to predict? *Statistical Science*, v. 25, n. 3, p. 289–310, 2010. DOI:
1513 <https://doi.org/10.1214/10-STS330>.
- 1514 SILVA, C.; GOMES, F.; SANTOS, J.; SANTOS, C. Uma análise comparativa das técnicas de
1515 machine learning: regressão logística, árvores de decisão, Random Forest e SVM. *Apoena*, v. 7,
1516 p. 501–511, 2023. Available at: <https://publicacoes.unijorge.com.br/apoena/article/view/183>.
- 1517 SILVA JR., L. SupplementaryMaterials: Tools for Speech Science Research. *Zenodo*, 2026. DOI:
1518 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19421930>.
- 1519 SILVA JR., L.; BARBOSA, P. Foreign accent and forensic speaker identification in voice
1520 lineups: the influence of acoustic features based on prosody. *Journal of Visualized Experiments*,
1521 n. 211, p. 1–21, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3791/66313>.
- 1522 SILVA JR., L.; BARBOSA, P. A. Voice disguise and foreign accent: prosodic aspects of English
1523 produced by Brazilian Portuguese speakers. *Journal of Experimental Phonetics*, v. 32, p. 195–
1524 226, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1344/efe-2023-32-195-226>.
- 1525 SILVA JR., L.; BARBOSA, P. A. Foreign accent and L2 speech rhythm of English: a pilot study
1526 based on metric and prosodic parameters. In: *Proceedings of the 2nd Brazilian Prosody*
1527 *Conference*. v. 1. 2022. p. 41–50. Available at:
1528 http://www.periodicos.letras.ufmg.br/index.php/anais_coloquio/article/view/34734.
- 1529 SILVA JR., L.; BARBOSA, P. A. Speech rhythm of English as L2: an investigation of prosodic
1530 variables on the production of Brazilian Portuguese speakers. *Journal of Speech Sciences*, v. 8, n.
1531 2, p. 37–57, 2019. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20396/joss.v8i2.14996>.
- 1532 SILVA JR., L.; BARBOSA, P.; MONTE, J. PROTOSODY: A Semi-Automated Protocol for
1533 Experimental Prosody Research. In: *Proceedings of Speech Prosody 2024*, p. 1245-1249, DOI:
1534 <https://doi.org/10.21437/SpeechProsody.2024-251>.
- 1535 SILVA JR., L.; SILVA, J.; MEER, P. Prosodic aspects of Brazilian L2 English: A comparison of
1536 duration-based rhythm and F0 measures with American English, Indian English, and Brazilian
1537 Portuguese. In: *Proceedings of Speech Prosody 2024*, v. 7, p. 101-105, 2024, DOI:
1538 <https://doi.org/10.21437/SpeechProsody.2024-21>.
- 1539 SILVEIRA, G.; ALBERT, A.; GRICE, M. Probing prosodic differences between two regional
1540 varieties of Brazilian Portuguese. In: *Proceedings of Interspeech 2025*, p. 2935-2939, 2025. DOI:
1541 <https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2025-1863>.
- 1542 TATMAN, R. Gender and dialect bias in YouTube's automatic captions. In: ACL WORKSHOP
1543 ON ETHICS IN NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING (EthNLP), 1., 2017, Valencia.
1544 *Proceedings of the First ACL Workshop on Ethics in Natural Language Processing*. Stroudsburg:

- 1545 Association for Computational Linguistics, 2017. p. 53–59. DOI:
1546 <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/W17-1606>.
- 1547 TATMAN, R.; KASTEN, C. Effects of talker dialect, gender & race on accuracy of Bing Speech
1548 and YouTube automatic captions. In: INTERSPEECH 2017, 2017, Stockholm. *Proceedings of*
1549 *Interspeech 2017*. [S.l.]: International Speech Communication Association, 2017. p. 934–938.
1550 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2017-1746>.
- 1551 TEIXEIRA, L. A. A multidimensional analysis of English-L2 rhythm development. *Ilha do*
1552 *Desterro*, v. 76, n. 3, p. 223–250, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5007/2175-8026.2023.e94742>.
- 1553 THOMAS, E. R. *Sociophonetics: An introduction*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011.
- 1554 TORGBI, M.; CLAYMAN, A.; SPEIGHT, J.; MADABUSHI, H. Adapting Whisper for regional
1555 dialects: Enhancing public services for vulnerable populations in the United Kingdom. In:
1556 SCHERRER, Y.; JAUHAINEN, T.; LJUBEŠIĆ, N.; NAKOV, P.; TIEDEMANN, J.;
1557 ZAMPIERI, M. (ed.). *Proceedings of the 12th Workshop on NLP for Similar Languages,*
1558 *Varieties and Dialects (VarDial 2025)*. New York: Association for Computational Linguistics,
1559 2025. p. 29–38. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.08502>.
- 1560 VAN ROSSUM, G.; DRAKE JR., F. L. *Python 3 reference manual*. Scotts Valley: CreateSpace,
1561 2009.
- 1562 WASSINK, A. B.; GANSEN, K.; BARTHOLOMEW, A. Uneven success: Automatic speech
1563 recognition and ethnicity-related dialects. *Speech Communication*, v. 140, p. 50–70, 2022. DOI:
1564 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.specom.2022.03.009>.
- 1565 WIELING, M.; TIEDE, M.; TOMASCHEK, F. Quantitative identification of dialect-specific
1566 articulatory settings. *Journal of Phonetics*, v. 61, p. 1–15, 2017. DOI:
1567 <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4990951>.
- 1568 WHITE, L.; MATTYS, S. L. Calibrating rhythm: First language and second language studies.
1569 *Journal of Phonetics*, v. 35, n. 4, p. 501–522, 2007. DOI:
1570 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2007.02.003>.
- 1571 YAEGER-DROR, M.; FAGYAL, Z. Analyzing prosody: Best practices for the analysis of
1572 prosody. In: DI PAOLO, M.; YAEGER-DROR, M. (eds.). *Sociophonetics: a student's guide*.
1573 London: Routledge, p. 119–130, 2011.
- 1574 YARKONI, T.; WESTFALL, J. Choosing prediction over explanation in psychology: Lessons
1575 from machine learning. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, v. 12, n. 6, p. 1100–1122, 2017.
1576 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691617693393>.
- 1577 ZHANG, Z. Speech feature selection and emotion recognition based on weighted binary cuckoo
1578 search. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, v. 60, p. 1499–1507, 2021. DOI:
1579 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2020.11.004>.
- 1580 ZHANG, C.; JEPSON, K.; LOHFINK, G.; ARVANITI, A. Comparing acoustic analyses of
1581 speech data collected remotely. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, v. 149, n. 6, p.
1582 3910–3916, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0005132>.